

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

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Abbreviations

SSO: single sign-on

Executive summary

This document describes the model workflow and rationale for impact evaluation in the case of citizen-science projects. This document presents a detailed, technical description of the MICS platform and interfaces. The platform’s workflow starts with creating a project page, allowing users to represent a citizen-science project on the MICS platform and access the impact assessment framework and tools. This document describes the first platform-interfaces and -elements that a user encounters when accessing the MICS platform and describes them for a first-time user. They represent the first step in the workflow.

This document then presents the next step in the workflow to evaluate the impact of citizen science. It describes the development of input features to capture the information required regarding a project’s inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts to fully model the impact over five domains. It also describes the process of operationalising the input features into questions, presented through interfaces of the MICS platform so users can access the impact-assessment tools of MICS. This document also includes a detailed methodological description of how the interface for capturing data was developed and the elements of entering content-related data (one of the main steps in the workflow).

This document reflects on the current status of the development of the algorithms (called Alquimics). MICS includes two types of algorithms, one based on explicit rules and one on machine learning. These algorithms enter the main workflow when content-related data (input features) are entered. The content-related data are the input of the algorithms. The output of the algorithms are impact scores, which are used in the interface presenting the impact assessment.

Finally, this document presents the visual elements of the impact-assessment report resulting from running Alquimics. The final part of the MICS platform workflow is the output users receive – the

reward for their time and effort in setting up a project and supplying the MICS assessment framework with the information required to evaluate impact. The platform's output is presented to the user as a report displayed on screen and downloadable as a pdf that links to the specific-project page, giving a detailed breakdown of the impact in each domain, with recommendations to improve.

The main implications of this deliverable for other WPs and tasks in MICS and in future developments are that this document will be used to guide the implementation of the MICS platform in the remaining execution period of the project and potentially after the end of the project if in the future the MICS platform will be updated or upgraded.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background on MICS

The MICS project develops approaches and tools to assess citizen-science impacts. These approaches and tools can help plan and implement projects in ways that lead to more robust results.

The MICS project specifically aims to:

- provide comprehensive, participatory and inclusive metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts;
- implement an impact-assessment knowledge-base through toolboxes for methods application, information visualisation, and delivery to decision makers, citizens and researchers;
- improve the effectiveness of nature-based solutions through test-site development and citizen-science tool validation;
- generate new approaches that strengthen the role of citizen science in supporting research and development;
- foster a citizen-science approach to increase the extent to which policy makers take up scientific evidence through recommendations and guidelines.

The result is an integrated platform where these metrics and instruments are available for use by anyone involved in a citizen-science project wanting to understand its impact, whether at the planning stage or several years after the project's conclusion. The MICS project adopts and adapts the best practice generated by the Ground Truth 2.0 project in the co-creation of hands-on citizen science validated in five case-study sites across Europe, resulting in a comprehensive conceptual framework and clear recommendations for those involved in citizen-science projects. The five sites (in the UK, Italy, Hungary and Romania) explore the co-creation of citizen science in regions with differing needs, contexts, and approaches to environment management (for example, river restoration and nature-based solutions), and with various levels of citizen-science application. For instance, in Western Europe, river restoration is increasingly carried out within an ecosystem-based management framework at river or catchment scale; in Southern Europe, river restoration tends to be issue-specific with some ecosystem relevance; in Central and Eastern Europe, river restoration is about ecosystem protection and related to existing infrastructure.

1.2 Purpose: a model for impact evaluation

This deliverable sits between WP2 and WP3 and presents the model workflow to evaluate the impact of citizen science and how to implement such a model. MICS developed this model within WP2, and previous versions of it have been presented in the output of WP2 of the project:

- Deliverable 2.1: A report about identified research results
- Deliverable 2.2 and 2.3: Reports detailing impact-assessment methods adapted to citizen science
- Deliverable 2.4: The MICS corpus of knowledge
- Deliverable 2.5: A multilingual ontology
- Deliverable 2.7: The finalised version of the conceptual framework

Here, how this model is being and will be implemented in the MICS web-based platform is described. The perspective of this document is technical (rather than conceptual) and focused on interfaces and user experience. Figure 1 outlines the **user impact-assessment workflow through the MICS platform** (typically, a *user* here is the coordinator of a citizen-science project), starting by registering and creating a space for a project, through to answering a set of questions (about impact indicators and project characteristics) and receiving a report on the impact of the project. The super elements of this impact-assessment workflow are:

- interface for the project-page creation (including landing pages and social login);
- interface to capture data (including general questions, a domain map and domain questions);
- database containing the data captured and other necessary data;
- algorithms to measure impact;
- interface to present the impact assessment.

MICS Platform: Interface flowchart

Landing pages:

Differ slightly depending on if you are registered or not

Project page:

Top half: Linked to info, collected in 'create a project'
Bottom half: Display of impact Output

Transition questions:

A set of questions describing the project

Domain map:

Progress visualisations etc.

Domain questions:

Different backgrounds etc. for each domain, with specifically design question 'pop-up' interfaces

Output:

On screen and pdf download

Figure 1: Mics platform interface flowchart

More in detail, these super elements include (see Figure 1):

- **Landing pages:** The interface displayed to the user when visiting the platform's home page: [mics.tools]. It shows several existing projects on the platform, allowing users to investigate what the platform offers. From here, a user can register on the platform, and create a space for a new project.
- **Project page:** A space for a project to be shared. It contains descriptive information about the project and the project impact, if any assessment has taken place, and allows the users to tailor the space, giving them ownership.
- **General questions (aka transition questions):** When starting the assessment process (accessed from the project page), the user first is presented with a set of broad, descriptive questions regarding the project, to ease the user into the process.
- **Domain map:** After completing the general questions, the user will be presented with the domain-map interface. MICS assesses the impact of a project across five domains: environment, economy, science, governance and society. From the domain map, the users can decide which questions associated with which domain they wish to complete first.
- **Domain questions:** When selecting a domain from the domain-map interface, the user will then be presented with the relevant domain interface, with questions related to that domain. Even if a question appears in just one domain, it can also be related to other domains. Domains are only used to graphically group questions for the benefit of human users; this grouping does not influence data processing in any way. The questions are displayed across a route or path, with certain logic linking them. Pop-ups with additional information might be shown as questions are completed and data are collected.
- **Output:** Users can access a report on the project's impact on completing or partially completing the assessment process. This report will take two forms: a summary report and a full report, giving a detailed breakdown of the impact in each domain, with recommendations to improve.

1.3 Platform's technology

Core to the principles of the MICS project are accessibility and the sharing of resources. The structure of the MICS platform is no exception, with open-source repositories, servers and development frameworks being utilised for both the front- and the back-end of the system. The following technologies have been used in the MICS platform development:

- **Apache:** free and open-source cross-platform web server software. Apache is developed and maintained by an open community of developers.
- **MariaDB:** a community-developed, commercially-supported fork of the MySQL relational database management system, intended to remain free and open-source software under the GNU General Public License.
- **Laravel:** a free, open-source PHP web framework for developing web applications following the model-view-controller architectural pattern.
- **Vue:** an open-source JavaScript framework for building user interfaces and single-page applications.

- [D3](#): a JavaScript library for producing dynamic, interactive data visualizations in web browsers. It makes use of *scalable vector graphics*, HTML5, and *cascading style sheets* standards.
- [Greensock](#): an industry-standard JavaScript animation library to craft high-performance animations that work in every major browser.

The use of open-source technologies as listed above will also ensure the sustainability of the MICS platform, allowing future development and updates to be performed using standardised protocols, and at little to no cost.

1.4 Structure of the report

This report is organised as follows. Following this introductory section, section 2 presents the model for the interface for the project-page creation, including landing pages and social login. Section 3 presents the interface's model to capture impact-related data, including general questions, a domain map and the domain-specific questions. Section 4 presents the model for the algorithm for impact assessment: Alquimics. Finally, section 5 describes the model for the interface to show the impact assessment.

2 Model for developing an interface for the project-page creation (including landing pages and social login)

This section presents a detailed, technical description of the MICS platform and interfaces for creating a project page, allowing users to represent a citizen-science project on the MICS platform and access the impact assessment framework and tools. The section describes the first platform interfaces and elements that a user encounters when accessing the MICS platform, and describes them for a first-time user. They represent the first step in the workflow.

2.1 Social login interface

The MICS platform requires the user to sign in to access part of the tools and functions of the impact assessment process. For signed-in users, the platform can keep track of progress, allow personalisation of the project space, and tailor assessment outputs to the user. Figure 2 outlines the appearance of the MICS platform sign-in interface.

A single sign-on (SSO) process is used to make the registration process as seamless as possible and to reduce the amount of data the MICS platform collects regarding the user. SSO is an authentication scheme that allows users to log in with a single ID and password to several independent software systems. SSO allows the user to log in once and access services without re-entering authentication factors. For MICS, the software systems supported are Facebook, Google, Twitter, LinkedIn and GitHub. The SSO process collects the minimum possible information about the user, basically the email address, which is used to identify returning users (see Figure 3).

Welcome to MICS
Measuring the impact of citizen science

MICS is an integrated platform of metrics and instruments created to measure the costs and benefits of citizen science. These metrics consider the impacts of citizen science on five domains:

Science Environment Economy Governance Society

MICS allows you to:

- Assess** the impact of your citizen science project, through metrics and indicators across five domains.
- Evaluate** the impact of your project from conception to realisation and beyond, seeing how impact changes over time and discovering opportunities to improve it further.
- Compare** your impact to similar projects and disciplines both regionally and internationally.
- Share** your impact with your communities, stakeholders, funders and policy makers.

Log in to MICS - You must log in to create a page for a project.

Impact assessment

Science Environment The economy Governance Society

Sign in with Facebook
Sign in with Google
Sign in with Twitter
Sign in with LinkedIn
Sign in with Microsoft
Sign in with GitHub

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Figure 2: MICS platform sign-in interface

← Apps with access to your account

Third-party apps with account access

You gave these sites and apps access to some of your Google Account data, including info that may be sensitive. Remove access for those you no longer trust or use. [Learn about the risks](#)

 SAMSUNG Account Has some account access

Signing in with Google

You use your Google Account to sign in to these sites and apps. They can view your name, email address, and profile picture. [Learn more](#)

Google Account sign-in prompts

Allow Google to offer a faster way to sign in with your Google Account on supported third-party sites

 SAMSUNG Account

 MICS tools

REMOVE ACCESS

Has access to:

 Basic account info

See your personal info, including any personal info you've made publicly available

See your primary Google Account email address

Homepage:

<https://mics.tools/>

Figure 3: MICS's access to a user's Google account if Google is used in SSO

Table 1 outlines the significant elements of the sign-in interface, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 1: Register interface elements

Interface element	Description and function
<p>Header text</p>	<p>Title of the interface, with a hardcoded description of the MICS platform and its use. The colours used are those of the MICS branding guide and will be consistent throughout the platform.</p>
<p>Impact assessment image</p>	<p>Static image showing the five domains across which impact is measured. The colours used for each domain will be consistent as domains are visualised throughout the platform.</p>
<p>SSO interactive buttons per software system</p>	<p>Interactive buttons for each SSO provider (Facebook, Google, Twitter, LinkedIn, Microsoft (to be confirmed) and GitHub), taking the user to the sign-on process for that provider</p>
<p>Bottom banner</p>	<p>The banner across the bottom of the interface, containing the EU-funding notice and Creative Commons licence (Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0))</p>

2.2 Landing page

As the name suggests, the MICS platform landing page is the first interface the user sees when accessing the platform URL [mics.tools]. From here, the user can access information about the

platform, see examples of existing projects already on the platform, and view project impact-assessment outcomes. The appearance and functionality of the landing page will slightly differ depending on if the user has signed into the platform or not.

Figure 4 outlines the appearance of the MICS-platform landing page interface for a user who has already registered with the platform.

Figure 4: MICS-platform landing page interface

Table 2 outlines the significant elements of the landing page interface, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 2: Landing page interface elements

Interface element	Description and function
<p>Header banner</p>	<p>Standard header banner with the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search: a button that allows users to search for projects via text entry • Logout/sign-in: a button that will enable the user to sign in or out as appropriate

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Username (James Sprinks): name of the user that is currently signed in • User Image: an image of the user that is signed in
<p>Header text</p>	<p>Title of the interface, with a hardcoded description of the MICS platform and its use. The colours used are those of the MICS branding guide and will be consistent throughout the platform.</p>
<p>Upper left menu</p>	<p>Standard menu on left of screen, with the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home: link to the MICS project website or the home of the platform (to be decided) • About: link to the MICS project website’s ‘About’ page [https://www.mics.tools/about-mics] • Projects: link to a list of projects (to be better defined) • Tools: link to a description of how the assessment process works, and other tools (to be better defined) • Your projects: a list of users’ current projects – linked to their project page • ‘Create a project’: takes the user to the “create a project” process (see section 2.3)
<p>Sort projects menu</p>	<p>By clicking on one of the disciplines listed (Arts, Science, etc.), the user can view projects from that discipline only (derived from the MICS platform database, through information gathered during the ‘create a project’ process (see 2.3).</p>

<p>Project display</p>	<p>A grid display of existing projects on the MICS platform created by existing users. It includes the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Featured projects: a row of projects, selected by when completed, how much of the assessment process has been completed, current topical relevance (to be better defined) • Project list: list of projects already existing on the MICS platform • Sort button: allows the user to sort the project list alphabetically, by start date, by end date (to be better defined) • ‘Take a look’ button: takes the user to the project page for that project (see 2.4) • Project logos: Each project in the featured projects and project list has a logo displayed, taken from the ‘create a project’ process (see 2.3). • Project background: Each project in the featured projects and project list has a background image displayed, taken from the ‘create a project’ process (see 2.3).
<p>Bottom banner</p>	<p>The banner across the bottom of the interface, containing EU-funding notice and Creative Commons licence.</p>

2.3 “Create a project” interface

Once a user has signed into the MICS platform, through the landing page, they can create a space for a citizen-science project. They do this through the ‘create a project’ interface, and supply the MICS platform with descriptive information to display to other users through the landing-page and project-page interfaces.

Figure 5 outlines the appearance of the ‘create a project’ interface.

Search

logout

James Sprinks

Create a project page

Connect your project, yourself and your cause to the worldwide community of citizen science.

Project name (the formal name of your project as appears on the project page)

Max 128 characters

Short name (to appear in menus and URLs)

Project topic (let us know the topics your project involves)

Max 20 characters

Logo image (an image to appear on your project page and in menus)

Upload logo image

Banner image (a cover photo or image to appear on your project page)

Upload banner image

Next

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Search

logout

James Sprinks

Create a project page

Connect your project, yourself and your cause to the worldwide community of citizen science.

Project description (introduction to the project, to display on the project page)

Max 500 characters

Short description (one sentence description for busy readers!)

Max 200 characters

Contact name (who to contact if someone wants to know more about the project)

Contact email

Project URL (link to website or page for more project information)

Next

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Figure 5: MICS platform 'create a project' interface – comprising of three question sets

Table 3 outlines the significant elements of the 'create a project' page interface, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 3: 'Create a project' page interface elements

Interface element	Description and function
Header banner 	See Table 2.
Header text Create a project page Connect your project, yourself and your cause to the worldwide community of citizen science.	Title and a brief description of the use
Project image 	Static image for aesthetic reasons

Question batch 1

Project name (the formal name of your project as appears on the project page)
 Max. 128 characters

Short name (to appear in menus and URLs)
 Max. 20 characters

Project topic (let us know the topics your project involves)
 Max. 20 characters

Logo image (an image to appear on your project page and in menus)

Banner image (a cover photo or image to appear on your project page)

The first batch of questions to gather descriptive information regarding the project, comprising of:

- Project name: the formal name of the project (text entry)
- Short name: to appear in menus and URLs (text entry)
- Project topic: the topics that the project involves (from a curated list)
- Logo image: to appear on project page and menus (uploaded image file)
- Banner image: a cover photo to appear on the project page (uploaded image file)

Question batch 2

Project description (introduction to the project, to display on the project page)
 Max. 500 characters

Short description (one sentence description for busy readers!)
 Max. 100 characters

Contact name (who to contact if someone wants to know more about the project)

Contact email

Project URL (link to website or page for more project information)

The second batch of questions to gather descriptive information regarding the project, comprising of:

- Project description: Introduction to the project, displayed on the project page (text entry, max. 500 characters)
- Short description: a one-sentence summary of the project (text entry, max 100 characters)
- Contact name: who to contact for more information on the project (text entry)
- Contact email: to reach the above (text entry, email rules)
- Project URL: link to the project website for more information (text entry, URL rules)

Question batch 3

Project location

Project organisers location (coordinators, partners - location by country)

Participants location (either worldwide, continent, or country)

Observations location (if different from participants location)

Third batch of questions to gather descriptive information regarding the project, comprising of:

- Project organisers location: coordinators, partners – located by country (drop-down, multiple selection)
- Participants location: either worldwide, continent or country (drop-down, multiple choice)
- Observations location: either worldwide, continent or country (drop-down, multiple choice) (usually, same as participants)

Bottom banner

See Table 2.

A novel feature of the MICS platform is its handling of location in the citizen science context. While most existing platforms treat this as a singular entry, the MICS platform will recognise that location can have different meanings for different projects. To capture this, coordinators will enter the project's location in terms of its management (partners, coordinator), its participants, or the data (observations) collected.

2.4 “Project page” interface

The MICS platform project page interface represents one of the most complex and essential parts of the platform. It acts as the area where the user can take ownership, and tailor the page for the project. This is done through the information collected on the ‘create a project’ interface, and the project page also provides access to the MICS assessment framework. After completing, either fully or partially, the assessment process, the impact of the project is shared on the project page, and reports and summary statistics become accessible to other MICS platform users.

Figure 6 outlines the appearance of the “project page” interface.

Figure 6: MICS platform's "project page"

Table 4 outlines the significant elements of the "project page" interface, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 4: Project page interface elements

Interface Element	Description and function
Header banner	See Table 2.

Upper left menu

Standard menu on left of screen, with the following functions:

- Project logo: as uploaded by user during the 'create a project' interface (see 2.3)
- 'Create a new project': Takes the user to the 'create a project' process (see 2.3)
- Home: See Table 2.
- About: See Table 2.
- Projects: See Table 2.
- Tools: See Table 2.

Project descriptives

Upper part of interface, with the following elements:

- Project banner: banner image as uploaded by user during 'create a project' process (see 2.3)
- Project information: descriptive information as entered by the user, including start date, end date, contact name, funding source, funding amount, project URL and topic
- Welcome message: hardcoded message welcoming user to their new page
- Project description: paragraph describing the project, submitted by user during 'create a project' process (see 2.3)
- Project map: map of project locations, switchable between organiser location, participant location and observation location, as entered by user during 'create a project' process (see 2.3)

Lower left menu

Standard menu on left of screen, with the following functions (to be confirmed):

- Start new impact assessment: allows the user to start/continue the impact assessment process, or restart it (a warning/confirmation will appear that restarting it will replace any current work done)

<p>Impact Assessment Tools</p> <p>Start new impact assessment</p> <p>Domain map</p> <p>Economy</p> <p>Environment</p> <p>Governance</p> <p>Science</p> <p>Society</p> <p>Summary report</p> <p>Full report</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain map: a link to the domain map interface • Economy: a link to the economy domain question interface • Environment: a link to the environment domain question interface • Governance: a link to the governance domain question interface • Science: a link to the science domain question interface • Society: a link to the society domain question interface • Summary report: allows the user to visualise/download a summary report of their impact assessment (pdf) • Full report: allows the user to visualise/download the full report of their impact assessment (pdf)
<p>Impact assessment content</p> <p>The screenshot displays a dashboard for impact assessment. At the top, there is a 'Progress to next level' bar. Below it, 'Current project impact' is shown with a circular gauge and a 'Total Score' of 34. To the right, there are progress bars for different domains. At the bottom, there are several badges representing achievements, some with plant pots and some with ribbons.</p>	<p>Lower part of the interface, showing user progress through the assessment process. Functions and elements include (to be confirmed):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progress to next level: shows users progress to next level. Points awarded for questions answered, badges attained etc. • Current project impact: shows users their current score in each domain and overall, based on the questions they have answered so far (see section 4) • Score rings: shows users how many questions the user has answered in each domain (percentage) • Progress bars: shows users how many questions the user has answered in each domain interface (percentage) • Plant pots: shows users when they last updated the project's impact assessment (colour shows timespan) • Badge progress 1: indicates badges user has achieved / is yet to achieve, including: impact assessment started, domain complete (x5), and all domains completed. Colourisation denotes that a badge has been earned; black and white means yet to be attained. • Badge progress 2: indicates badges user has achieved / is yet to achieve, including: 6 months' service, 1 years' service, 2 years' service
<p>Bottom banner</p>	

3 Model for an interface to capture data (including the transition questions, the domain map and the domain questions)

This section presents the next step in the workflow to evaluate the impact of citizen science. It describes the development of input features to capture the information required regarding a project's inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts to fully model the impact over the five domains. It also describes the process of operationalising the input features into questions, presented through three interfaces of the MICS platform so users can access the impact-assessment tools of MICS. The section includes a detailed methodological description of how the interface for capturing data was developed and the elements of one of the main steps in the workflow (entering content-related data, rather than project background information as in section 2).

3.1 Model for developing input features for impact assessment

3.1.1 Background

The input features are used to capture information about a project and are used as inputs for Alquimics, the algorithm used in the MICS platform. The input features are based on the indicators described in the MICS conceptual framework (reported in MICS D2.7) and draw on the results from a systematic review of the citizen science literature on impact assessment methodologies (reported in MICS D2.2). In contrast to the format of the indicators presented in MICS D2.7, the input features are presented as closed questions with a pre-defined set of answer options. This means the input features can be implemented as questions in the platform without free-text fields. The advantages of this format are threefold. Firstly, avoiding free text makes it quicker and easier for users to answer the questions. Secondly, because the answers are pre-defined, each can be used as input to a neural network. Thirdly, there is no need for natural language processing or other expensive text analyses to assess the project's impacts.

3.1.2 Input feature development

An initial set of approximately 150 input features were either directly selected or based around those from several reputable sources; the ECSA characteristics of citizen science, the MoRRI project indicators, the SDGs, and a number highly-cited literature reviews, particularly Kieslinger's 2017 paper, "The Challenge of Evaluation: An Open Framework for Evaluating Citizen Science Activities".

3.1.3 User feedback

The questions used to collect data need to be easy to understand so that MICS platform users can answer the question without help or supervision. It was, therefore, essential to test the initial set of input features with potential users of the platform to gather feedback on the input features and refine the wording of the questions and set of answers. A series of semi-structured interactions were arranged with a group of 12 citizen-science project coordinators. The 12 project coordinators were recruited from within the MICS consortium partners and from a small group of people who had already expressed interest in contributing to the development of the MICS toolbox and who had taken part in interviews for the MICS project in February 2020 (reported in MICS D2.2). First, a workshop was held with three project coordinators, followed by nine interviews with other project coordinators. All data were collected in line with the MICS ethics requirements, and a signed copy of the MICS informed consent sheet was collected where necessary.

3.1.4 Workshop

The workshop provided an opportunity to “road-test” an initial set of input features before holding interviews with external coordinators. The workshop aimed to gather feedback on the structure and content of the input features (both questions and answers) and to collect detailed data from three project coordinators, which could be used to initially design, test and train Alquimics, the impact assessment algorithm.

The workshop took place in person on Monday 12th April and was held in a meeting room at the Earthwatch office in Oxford, UK. In total, the session lasted just over four hours, including regular breaks for refreshments. The workshop was coordinated by two members of the MICS consortium, Sasha Woods and Stephen Parkinson. Two facilitators were present for the workshop because it can be hard to engage in a discussion whilst taking notes: one to read out the questions and lead the conversation and the other to take notes. Three members of staff from Earthwatch were invited via email to participate in the workshop, and all agreed. Each of the participants answered the questions from their perspective as coordinator of a citizen science project:

- Luigi Ceccaroni (Citclops)
- James Sprinks (Mars in Motion)
- Isabel Bishop (FreshWater Watch)

The workshop began with a brief welcome and introduction, which included outlining the objectives and structure of the interview and explaining how the data collected would be used. The main content of the workshop was structured around the input features distributed in six Microsoft Forms. One form contained a set of introductory “General” questions, and the remaining forms contained questions relating to each of the MICS domains. Examples of the Microsoft Forms used in the workshops and interviews are presented in Annexes 1-6. The forms were answered in the following order:

1. General
2. Society
3. Governance
4. Economy
5. Environment
6. Science

Participants were guided to answer the questions in all of the forms and were invited to give their feedback on each input feature and on the structure of each questionnaire. The design of the workshop was based on “think aloud” protocols. The workshop organisers introduced each form and then read out each question, making sure all the participants were answering the questions simultaneously. Participants were encouraged to comment on what they liked and disliked in the questions and available answers. And going through each question systematically ensured participants had the time and opportunity to give feedback on each input feature.

While participants were able to provide comments at any stage, prompt questions were also used to elicit feedback on the questionnaire's input features and overall structure. The following list of questions was written on a flip-chart and placed in view of all the participants and was designed to gather feedback on each input feature:

- Does the question feel relevant to your project?
- Is the question easy to understand?
 - Do you need further information to answer the question?

- Would more examples or prompts be helpful?
- Are any answer options missing in the question? If you selected “Other”, what would your answer be in a free-text field?
- Can you answer the question with the information you have currently available, or would you need to look things up or ask other people?
- Is there any way you can think of to improve the question?

Participants were invited to consider these prompts whilst answering each question, but the prompts were only read out and explained at the start of the workshop. The prompts were intended to trigger a meaningful discussion, but participants could also make comments without prompts and were explicitly encouraged to do so.

Once the participants had answered all the questions in each Microsoft Form, they were asked another series of questions about that section as a whole. All of these questions were asked at the end of every section:

- Are you surprised that we didn’t ask a particular question in this domain?
- Did the order of the questions make sense?
- Did any questions seem out of place or not relevant either to the domain or to the impact of your project?
- Did you find any questions particularly enjoyable, interesting or thought-provoking?

Finally, at the end of the workshop, the participants were asked a last set of questions about their experience of providing answers for all the input features:

- How did you find the experience of answering so many questions?
- How do you think the experience would have been different if we weren’t here in the same room? Would it have been easier or harder?

At the end of the workshop, participants were also introduced to some of the MICS project's recent progress, including mock-ups for the MICS platform.

3.1.5 Interviews

The semi-structured interviews built on the insights gained from the initial internal workshop provided another opportunity to test and refine the input features before they are implemented into the MICS platform. The interviews aimed to gather feedback on the structure and content of the input features (both questions and answers).

In total, nine interviews took place between April and June 2021. Eight of the interviews were held online using the GoToMeeting video-conferencing software, and one was held in person at the Earthwatch office in Oxford, UK. Each interview session lasted around five hours, including regular breaks for refreshments. Members of the MICS consortium carried out the interviews. As with the workshop, at least two interviewers were present at each interview, one to ask each of the questions and lead the discussion and the other to take notes. Each of the participants answered the questions from their perspective as coordinator of a citizen science project.

The interviews began with a brief welcome and introduction, which included outlining the objectives and structure of the interview and explaining how the data collected would be used. The main content of the interviews was structured around six Microsoft Forms (Annexes 1-6). Participants were guided through to answer the questions in all of the forms and were invited to give their feedback on each question and on the structure of each form. The interviewers introduced each form and then read out

each question, allowing time for the interviewee to answer the question and share any comments. The Microsoft Forms gave an excellent structure to the interview, ensuring that comments from each participant could be compared between interviews. The interview guide and session structure used for the interviews is shown in Annex 7.

Table 5 Order of domains for each project coordinator interviewed

Interview #	Order of domains in interview					
1	General	Science	Environment	Society	Economy	Governance
2	General	Environment	Science	Economy	Governance	Society
3	General	Society	Economy	Science	Governance	Environment
4	General	Governance	Economy	Environment	Society	Science
5	General	Economy	Governance	Environment	Science	Society
6	General	Science	Society	Governance	Environment	Economy
7	General	Environment	Governance	Science	Society	Economy
8	General	Society	Science	Environment	Economy	Governance
9	General	Economy	Environment	Society	Governance	Science
Domain	Occurrences of each domain in each position					
Society	2	1	2	2	2	2
Governance	1	2	2	2	2	2
Economy	2	2	1	2	2	2
Environment	2	2	2	2	2	1
Science	2	2	2	1	2	2

3.1.6 Data collection

Data on the participants responses was collected in three ways:

- The participants entered their answers to each question in the Microsoft Forms. All of these responses were captured and provide a dataset of information about each project. This data has been exported from Microsoft Forms and is stored in an Excel spreadsheet.
- Throughout the interview, the interviewers took notes on the participants feedback on each input feature. These notes were structured so that each comment can be associated to each question and section but also to the project coordinator who made the comment.
- The interviewers also recorded their own observations from the workshop and interviews (for example, how easily the participants answered particular questions).

Comments from the coordinators were not captured verbatim because, whilst they may be interest to analyse, they are not required to create a clear picture of project coordinators' opinion on each question and capturing or analysing this volume of information would be very resource intensive. After the workshop and each interview, the notes from the discussion were cleaned: all comments were spell-checked and, where necessary, converted to full sentences. Further observations from the interviewers were also added, where relevant.

3.1.7 Analysis

The process of input feature analysis had three main stages:

- Editing the questions based on the comments from the workshop and interviews
- Aligning the questions with indicators gathered from the literature review in WP2
- Generating new questions as necessary, based on gaps in the alignment

In this section, we describe these stages based on the **Economy domain**.

Three examples of how input features were edited are shown in the table below. In the first example, the question – taken from SDG 8.2 (Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation?) - received no negative feedback during the workshop or the interviews, and project coordinators answered it without difficulty. The final version of the question, therefore, remained the same as the original question. In the second example - taken from Ferri et al. (2020) (time invested by researchers in engaging and training citizens) - the question was considered unproblematic in the workshop but was flagged by one interviewee as combining two different impact indicators – training and engaging – and by another interviewee as being too vague. This question was modified to reflect the comments provided. The third example - taken from Kieslinger et al. (2017) (Does the project include any competitive advantage?) - was considered problematic in the workshop. After elaborating on what was meant by “competitive advantage” and providing one example, the question was still flagged in interviews as unclear, so a second example was added to the final version.

Table 6 Editing questions based on user feedback

Original question	Comment from workshop	Modified question	Comments from interview	Final question
Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation? (SDG 8.2)	-	-	-	Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation?
The studies that do focus on economic impacts related to citizen science (rather than citizen observatories) propose to consider the time invested by researchers in engaging and training citizens (Ferri et al., 2020)		How much time is invested by researchers in engaging and training citizens?	For us, training and engagement are different things . The training is a day. But ongoing engagement is harder to quantify; it's more continuous throughout the project. Maybe it would be good to split out the questions. We don't directly do it, but we provided all the materials and will continue producing them. I do spend time doing it, so I will answer yes. It is unclear whether this is what the question is asking or not; do I have to engage them in person. Hours and days in a week or across the length of the whole project. It would be good to clarify this in the answer options to know what you're answering.	How much time is invested by the project in training citizens? Training might involve identifying different species or planets, using equipment or sensors, or analysing data, and can include the production of training materials.

Does the project include any competitive advantage? (Kieslinger, 2017)	What does this mean? Need examples to help people to interpret the question. Competitive advantage on a commercial rather than a scientific level.	Does the project include any competitive advantage (on the economic rather than the scientific scale)? Here “competitive advantage” refers to factors that allow an organisation to produce outputs or services better or more cheaply than its rivals. For example , the incorporation of citizen science might provide a competitive advantage for the ecotourism providers in the tourism market	The examples are for the tourism market. Would marketing be involved here so the organisation can say we have volunteers collecting water quality worldwide? It’s good marketing material but isn’t directly related to the activities of HSBC. I understood that you were asking about a more apparent competitive advantage. This marketing/propaganda thing is important.	Does the project include any competitive advantage (on the economic rather than the scientific scale)? Here “competitive advantage” refers to factors that allow an organisation to produce outputs or services better or more cheaply than its rivals. For example, incorporating citizen science might provide a competitive advantage for the ecotourism providers in the tourism market; healthcare data might offer a competitive advantage for pharmaceutical companies.
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The methods by which WP2 conducted their literature review of impact assessment in citizen science and its results were described in detail in deliverable 2.7 “Finalised version of the conceptual framework”, and in When et al. (2021).

We used this framework to ensure even more significant alignment between the questions we had generated in WP3 and the literature assessed by WP2. Table 7 shows an example of this. Within the Economy domain, WP2 established an indicator cluster, “Innovation and research”, including questions such as, “How many IPRs related to COs and enabling technologies (patents, trademarks, copyright, other know-how rights) does your organization hold?”. We matched four questions from WP3 to this indicator cluster.

Finally, we generated new questions – for example, NEW028 in the table – to fill the gaps in our alignment and capture the missing information represented by the indicator cluster.

Table 7 Aligning questions to WP2

Indicator Cluster	Data collection items	Question ID	Question	Implementation
Innovation & research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How many IPRs related to COs and enabling technologies (patents, trademarks, copyright, other know-how rights) does your organization hold? EE102	EC091	Does the project involve commercial activities related to industry or academia?	
		EE102	Does the project have any economic potential to be exploited in the future (for example, new intellectual property with economic value, or new sensors with a clear market, or the prospect to employ new personnel)?	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How many CO-related research projects is your organization currently involved? EE103 • In total, what is your organization's budget (income & own investment) in these CO-related research projects? NEW028 	T013	Could you quantify the total funding received by the project (in £, € or \$)	
	EE103	Did the project generate related new projects or new project proposals?	
	NEW028	How much external funding was secured for these spin-off projects?	Implemented as question EE180

3.1.8 Results and ongoing work

The input feature development in WP3 and alignment to indicators established in WP2 resulted in a collection of 218 questions that are well-aligned to current literature and well-understood by project coordinators.

- General: 21 questions
- Society: 65 questions
- Governance: 33 questions
- Economy: 31 questions
- Environment: 20 questions
- Science: 48 questions

These questions, along with their answer options and help pop-ups, are listed in Annexes 8 - 13. The process of indicator analysis is continuing across all the MICS domains, and the input features will continue to be updated based on feedback and testing by users of the platform.

3.2 Transition questions interface

Accessed from the Project page interface (see 2.4), the Transition questions interface represents the start of the impact assessment process, allowing users to access metrics and instruments to evaluate the citizen science impacts of their project. The interface is designed to be a gentle introduction to the process, asking questions of a more demographic nature that should not require in-depth thinking or supplementary information.

Figure 7 outlines the appearance of the Transition questions interface.

Impact Assessment Tools: Measure the impact of this project

Before we can assess the impact of the project across the five domains, we need some general information to help us ensure the process and recommendations are suitable and in context.

2. What forms of knowledge does the project (as a whole) create?

- New data
- New analyses
- New written knowledge
- New methodologies
- New concepts
- Other forms of knowledge
- I do not know

Figure 7: MICS platform transition questions interface

Table 8 outlines the major elements that the Transition questions interface composes of, with a description of the functionality of each. Table 10 details the questions within this interface.

Table 8: Transition questions interface elements

Interface Element	Description and function
Header banner and description Impact Assessment Tools: Measure the impact of this project Before we can assess the impact of the project across the five domains, we need some general information to help us ensure the process and recommendations are suitable and in context.	Title and a brief description of the interface
Start position logo	Logo of the project being assessed, located at the start position and supplied by the user in 'create a project' interface

<p>Start</p>	
<p>Position marker</p>	<p>Marker visualisation showing which question should be answered next in the sequence</p>
<p>Question circle</p>	<p>Selectable question icon to display a question. Highlighted green if already answered, red if yet to be answered, or greyed out if disabled by question logic</p>
<p>Question route</p>	<p>Dynamically created route from question database associated with 'Transition' domain. Extends on screen as required to include all questions</p>
<p>End of route marker</p> <p>Domain map</p>	<p>Image of domain map interface, indicating the end of questions – clickable so user can navigate to domain map when questions completed</p>
<p>Question display</p>	<p>Interactive display of question selected by the user on the question route, with questions created from MICS question database and answers from possible answers database</p>

Table 9 Transition questions

Question	Answer	Help
<p>What forms of knowledge does the project as a whole create?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New data (quantitative or qualitative) • New analyses (including existing approaches applied to new data) • New methodologies (e.g. for data collection, 	

	<p>participant engagement, education)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New concepts • I don't know 	
What is the start date of the project? (If you don't know the exact start date just select the first day of the start month. It can be in the future. If the project starts with a grant, this is the start date of the funding.)	M/d/yyyy	
What is the end date of the project? (If you don't know the exact end date just select the last day of the end month).	M/d/yyyy	
What is the expected duration of the project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 1 year • 1-2 years • 3-4 years • 5 years or more • I don't know 	
Are participants currently able to contribute to citizen science activities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
How well can you estimate the number of observations collected by the project so far (observations as defined by the project)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know the approximate number* • I know the order of magnitude** • I have no idea about how many observations have been collected • I don't really know what observations are • Observations are not a significant element of the project, and quantifying them is not important 	
*How many observations have been collected so far?	number	
**How many observations have been collected so far?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • More than 300,000 	

<p>How many observations are collected in a typical recent year of active project? (If the project has been running for less than a year you can estimate the number).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • More than 3000 • Too difficult to estimate 	<p>To put the project's data collection in perspective just think that eBird collected 700 000 000 observations and iNaturalist 40 000 000. But that doesn't mean that you have less than 1% of the impact of these projects. Context is important and that's why we need to ask so many questions.</p>
<p>How well can you estimate the number of participants who have contributed to the project's citizen science activities?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know the approximate number* • I know the order of magnitude** • I don't know • Participants are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important 	
<p>*How many participants have contributed to the project's citizen science activities so far?</p>	<p>number</p>	
<p>**How many participants have contributed to the project's citizen science activities so far?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • More than 30,000 	
<p>How many participants contribute to citizen science activities in a typical year of active project? (If the project has been running for less than a year you can estimate the number).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • More than 30,000 • Too difficult to estimate 	<p>On average, in the project, each participant collects [(calculation) observation/participants] observations. In a typical long-tail situation, 10% of the participants would collect [(calculation to be defined) x] observations, and 90% would collect [(calculation to be defined) y] observations.</p>
<p>Including participants who have directly contributed to the citizen science activities, how many people have been engaged by the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • More than 300,000 • I don't know 	
<p>How well can you estimate the total external funding received by the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know the approximate number* • I know the order of magnitude** • The project did not receive external funding • I don't know 	

<p>*What is the total external funding received by the project? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]</p>	<p>number</p>	
<p>**What is the total external funding received by the project? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • 300,001-3,000,000 • More than 300,000,000 	
<p>How well can you estimate the total financial investment in the project (including internal funding)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know the approximate number* • I know the order of magnitude** • The project did not receive internal funding*** • I don't know 	
<p>*What is the total financial investment in the project including internal funding? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]</p>	<p>number</p>	
<p>**What is the total financial investment in the project including internal funding? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • 300,001-3,000,000 • More than 300,000,000 	
<p>***Is the project focused on one or more of the following five domains?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economy: the production and exchange of goods and services among economic agents • Environment: the bio-chemical-physical environment • Governance: the processes and institutions through which decisions are made, both informal and formal • Science and technology: the scientific process (method) as well as research more broadly; the scientific system, scientific paradigms and 	

	<p>resulting technological artefacts and standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Society: individuals as well as collective (societal) values, understanding, actions and well-being (including relationships) 	
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3.3 Domain map interface

The Domain map interface of the MICS platform acts as a central hub, allowing the user to navigate to questions that capture the impact of the project across the five domains: economy, environment, governance, science and society. It also acts as a place where the user can centre themselves, seeing their progress across the domains in terms of questions answered, and deciding which direction to take next. It is accessed from the Transition questions interface (see 3.2), or through the “project page” interface (see 2.4).

Figure 8 outlines the appearance of the Domain map interface.

Figure 8: MICS platform domain map interface

Table 10 outlines the major elements of the Domain map interface, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 10: Domain map interface elements

Interface Element	Description and function
<p>Header banner</p>	<p>Standardised banner used consistently throughout MICS platform</p>
<p>Right-hand text</p>	<p>Title and a brief description of the interface</p>
<p>Map visualisation</p>	<p>Map showing each of the five domains, along with a visualisation showing progress on each one. Each domain can be highlighted and selected, allowing the user to navigate to each set of domain questions</p>
<p>Progress meters</p>	<p>Visualisation showing the progress that the user has made per domain (as a number and percentage of questions answered)</p>

3.4 Domain question interface

The Domain question interfaces of the MICS platform are the interaction space where the majority of the information needed to evaluate the impact of a project is collected from the user. They include and present all of the questions adapted from the input features derived in section 3.1, including any logic required to remove/pre-fill questions and answers based on their relevance to the project being evaluated. There is one interface for each domain, accessible from both the Domain map interface (see 3.3) and the Project page interface (see 2.4).

Figure 9 outlines the appearance of the Domain question interface.

Figure 9: MICS-platform domain questions interface – without question selected (top), and with the question selected (bottom)

Table 11 outlines the major elements of the Domain question interfaces, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 11: Domain question interface elements

Interface Element	Description and function
Header banner	
	Standardised banner used consistently throughout MICS platform

<p>Question circle</p>	<p>An interactive icon that displays the domain question. Highlighted to display status: green for answered, red for yet to be answered, greyed out for disabled due to logic</p>
<p>Question route</p>	<p>Dynamically created route from question database associated with each of the five domains. Extends on screen as required to include all questions, with a different background representing each domain</p>
<p>Username and project logo</p>	<p>Visualisation displaying the user that is currently completing the questions, and for which project. Logo and username supplied by the user during 'create a project' process</p>
<p>Progress meter</p>	<p>Visualisation showing progress made within the current domain (as a percentage of the total questions answered)</p>
<p>Progress meters (other domains)</p>	<p>Visualisation showing progress made within other domains than the current displayed (as a percentage of the total questions answered)</p>
<p>Link buttons</p>	<p>Interactive buttons that allow the user to navigate to the Domain map interface, the project page interface, or get help</p>

Table 12 outlines the major elements of the Question pop-up interface, which appears when a question is selected by clicking on the Question circle (see Table 12), with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 12: Question pop-up interface elements

Interface Element	Description and function
<p>Question title</p>	<p>Title of the question, taken from the Question table of the MICS database</p>
<p>Question text</p>	<p>Question text, taken from the Question table of the MICS database</p>
<p>Possible answers</p>	<p>A list of the possible answers for the question, taken from the <i>Possible_answer</i> table of the MICS database</p>
<p>Question type tab</p>	<p>A tab with information describing the type of question, and how it should be answered. Types include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple choice • Single answer • Likert • Numerical • Date
<p>Navigation icons</p>	<p>Two navigation icons allowing the user to complete the question. The options are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Return to route: closes the Question pop-up interface and returns to the domain question interface. • Next question: Displays the next question in the domain (represented by the next question circle along the route)
<p>Help and Information pop-ups</p>	<p>Two icons that, when clicked by the user, display a pop of text as follows:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Help: Text that directly helps the user answer the question, updated as FAQs become known• Information: Broader information and links provided to the user around the question theme <p>The text is taken from the Question table of the MICS database.</p>
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3.5 Model for a database containing the data captured and other necessary data

The previous sections have outlined and given a technical description of the interfaces that allow a user to set up their project on the MICS platform, and supply information in order to evaluate its impact. This section will describe what could be termed as the ‘back-end’ of the platform – a model for a database to hold the information on the project. Through the output of this database, the MICS impact assessment tools and algorithm will be able to evaluate the impact of citizen science activities, feeding back to the database, which in turn presents the results to the user (see section 5).

The MICS database structure can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: MICS database structure

As can be seen, the database is made up of several tables, the central being the **Project** table – representing the core element of the MICS platform. Each table is made up of a number of fields that follow, where possible, the MICS ontology (D2.5, Ceccaroni *et al.* 2020) in terms of their nomenclature.

4 Model for an algorithm for impact assessment: Alquimics

This section reflects on the current status of the development of the algorithms. MICS includes two types of algorithms, one based on explicit rules and one on machine learning, as explained in more detail below. These algorithms enter the main workflow when content-related data (input features) are entered. The content-related data are the input of the algorithms. The output of the algorithms are impact scores, which are used in the interface presenting the impact assessment.

4.1 Introduction to Alquimics

Alquimics is the algorithm behind the MICS platform. It is being created through part handcrafting (a labour-intensive technique for programming that involves writing explicit rules and templates) part machine learning (a type of AI that learns to perform a task by analysing patterns in data).

The team is facing a defining question: Which parts of the platform's brain should be handcrafted and which should employ machine learning? Handcrafting is the more traditional approach, in which scientists painstakingly write extensive sets of rules to guide AI's understanding and assessments. Statistically-driven machine-learning methods, by contrast, have the computer teach itself to assess impact by learning from data.

Machine learning is a superior method for tackling so-called classification problems, in which neural networks find unifying patterns in noisy data. But, when translating indicators characterising citizen-science projects into impact assessment, machine learning has a long way to go. As such, the team finds itself struggling, like the tech world at large, to find the best balance between the two approaches.

To help Alquimics automatically generate impact assessments, the team will have at its disposal only 10-30 sets of instances of about 200 indicators (or input features).

So, the MICS team is writing extensive assessment-guiding rules. The team created five "impact domains": environment, economy, governance, science, and society. The MICS system is being engineered to know the core elements of each of the five domains and can bounce around among them. And the MICS team is assessing the option of dividing the platform's brain into a committee of smaller algorithms, each with a speciality of its own.

Impact assessment is a daunting challenge. It is especially tough for a machine-learning system because there usually is not a verifiably correct way to assess impact. Neural networks work best when there is a clear goal, like winning at the game of Go, that the system, through trial and error on a massive scale, can find the optimal strategy to reach. Impact assessment has no well-defined goal.

Initially, the MICS team is just guessing how much to weigh each metric. But, by the end of the project, a neural network will have learned to rejigger the weights automatically.

So, the team is taking a middle-of-the-road approach to mixing rules-based programming and machine learning into its system. The edge of the MICS platform with respect to existing systems is an interface and an interaction that people will enjoy. The system will ask questions about indicators and provide engaging, conversational feedback so the users can learn more about their projects and how to improve them to achieve a more substantial impact.

To achieve this, the team is handcrafting plenty of feedback language: "So tell me, is the project more about science or engagement?", and the like.

4.2 Implementation of Alquimics

Alquimics is a set of algorithms that take as input the characteristics of a citizen-science project and produce as output the numerical impact of that project in five domains. The algorithms are implemented in GNU Octave, a software featuring a high-level programming language, primarily intended for numerical computations. Octave helps solve linear and nonlinear problems numerically and perform other numerical experiments using a language that is mostly compatible with MATLAB. It is also frequently used as an artificial-intelligence language. Since it is part of the GNU Project, it is free software under the GNU General Public License terms. Alquimics is and will be public. It can be freely accessed and reused for any purpose and without restrictions. In the following, the main algorithm is described and commented on. To work, this main algorithm needs the following secondary algorithms, which are called in the code but are omitted here:

- `fmincg`
- `nnCostFunction`

- predict
- sigmoid
- sigmoidGradient

The main algorithm also needs to load the training data: a file for each project (e.g., X1, X2, X3) and a file with the impact of the projects used for training (Y). All these files are *comma-separated values* (CSV) files.

%% MICS - Alquimics - neural-network learning and prediction

%% Initialisation

clear; close all; clc

%% Setup of the parameters

Figure 11: This figure shows a simplified view of the Alquimics neural network. In the current implementation of Alquimics, the input layer (left, darker blue) is made of 3040 units, the hidden layer (centre, grey) of 4000 units and the output layer (right, lighter blue) of 5 units, one for each domain.

input_layer_size = 3040; % 152x20 (questions x options); 152 is the number of input features used in the first experiments; 20 is the maximum number of options for any particular question

hidden_layer_size = 4000; % 4000 hidden units

num_labels = 5; % 5 labels for the domains, from 1 to 5

%% ===== Part 1: Loading and visualising data =====

% We start by first loading and visualising the dataset.

% We work with a dataset that contains citizen-science project characteristics.

```

% Load training data
fprintf('Loading data...\n')
pause (1);
X1=csvread('X1.csv');
X2=csvread('X2.csv');
X3=csvread('X3.csv');

% Unroll and merge input matrices
X = [X1'(:)' ; X2'(:)' ; X3'(:)'];

y=csvread('Y.csv');
m = size(X, 1);

% Randomly select 2 data points to display
% sel = randperm(size(X, 1));
% sel = sel(1:3);
% disp(X(sel, :));

%% ===== Part 2: Loading parameters =====

% In this part, we randomly initialise the neural network parameters.
fprintf('\nInitialising neural-network parameters...\n')
pause (2);

% Initialise the weights into variables Theta1 and Theta2
epsilon_init1 = 0.029;
Theta1 = (2*epsilon_init1).*rand(4000,3041)-epsilon_init1;
epsilon_init2 = 0.039;
Theta2 = (2*epsilon_init2).*rand(5,4001)-epsilon_init2;

% Unroll parameters
initial_nn_params = [Theta1(:) ; Theta2(:)];

%% ===== Part 3: Compute cost (Feedforward) =====

% We first started by implementing the feedforward part of the neural network that returns the cost
only. This part of the code, which does not include regularisation and constitutes a weak, initial
implementation prone to overfitting, is only activated for debugging.

% nnCostFunction.m returns the cost.
fprintf('\nStarting neural network...\n')

```

```

pause (3);

% Weight regularization parameter (we set this to 0 here).

% lambda = 0;

% J = nnCostFunction(initial_nn_params, input_layer_size, hidden_layer_size, ...
%                   num_labels, X, y, lambda);

%fprintf(['Cost at initialisation parameters without regularisation: %f '...
%        '\n\n'], J);

%% ===== Part 4: Implement regularisation =====

% We now check the regularisation with the cost.

fprintf('\nCalculating cost function with regularisation (to avoid overfitting)... \n\n')

pause (3);

% Weight regularisation parameter (we set this to 1 here).

lambda = 1;

J = nnCostFunction(initial_nn_params, input_layer_size, hidden_layer_size, ...
                  num_labels, X, y, lambda);

fprintf(['Cost function corresponding to initialisation parameters: %f '...
        '\n'], J);

pause (3);

%% ===== Part 5: Sigmoid gradient =====

% We check the gradient for the sigmoid function.

fprintf('\nEvaluating sigmoid gradient... \n')

pause (2);

fprintf('\nSigmoid gradient at [-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]: ')

pause (1);

g = sigmoidGradient([-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]);

%fprintf('Sigmoid gradient evaluated at [-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]:\n ');

fprintf('%f ', g);

pause(4);

%% ===== Part 6: Training NN =====

% We have now all the code necessary to train a neural network. To train the neural network, we will
now use "fmincg".

```

% This advanced optimizer is able to train our cost functions efficiently as long as we provide it with the gradient computations.

```
fprintf('\n\nTraining neural network... \n\n')
```

% The MaxIter can be changed to a larger value to see how more training helps.

```
options = optimset('MaxIter', 5);
```

% Different values of lambda should be tried.

```
lambda = 2;
```

% Create "short hand" for the cost function to be minimized

```
costFunction = @(p) nnCostFunction(p, ...  
    input_layer_size, ...  
    hidden_layer_size, ...  
    num_labels, X, y, lambda);
```

% Now, costFunction is a function that takes in only one argument (the neural network parameters)

```
[nn_params, cost] = fmincg(costFunction, initial_nn_params, options);
```

% Obtain Theta1 and Theta2 back from nn_params

```
Theta1 = reshape(nn_params(1:hidden_layer_size * (input_layer_size + 1)), ...  
    hidden_layer_size, (input_layer_size + 1));
```

```
Theta2 = reshape(nn_params((1 + (hidden_layer_size * (input_layer_size + 1))):end), ...  
    num_labels, (hidden_layer_size + 1));
```

%% ===== Part 7: Implement predict =====

% After training the neural network, we use it to predict the labels, that is the impact in the five domains. The "predict" function uses the neural network to predict the labels of the training set (X). This lets us compute the training set accuracy. To measure the impact of a new project, this project's data set should be used instead of X in the following line of code.

```
pred = predict(Theta1, Theta2, X);
```

```
fprintf('\nTraining Set Accuracy: %f\n', mean(double(pred == y)) * 100);
```

5 Model for an interface to present the impact assessment

This section presents the visual elements of the impact-assessment report resulting from running Alquimics. The final part of the MICS platform workflow is the output users receive – the reward for their time and effort in setting up a project (see section 2) and supplying the MICS assessment framework with the information required to evaluate impact (see sections 3 and 4). The output of the platform is presented to the user through two interfaces:

- A summary report displayed on screen or downloadable as a pdf, that links to the project page (see 2.4).

- A full report as a pdf – giving a detailed breakdown of the impact in each domain, with recommendations to improve.

5.1 Impact assessment summary report interface

The impact assessment summary report interface is designed to give the user an easy to understand, visually attractive summary of the project's impact across the five domains. It can be accessed both on screen or downloaded as a pdf from the project page interface (see 2.4).

Figure 12 outlines the appearance of the Impact-assessment summary report interface.

FreshWaterWatch FreshWater Watch impact summary

This is an impact report of the citizen-science project FreshWater Watch. The scores displayed summarise the results of the assessment process designed by the MICS project. For more information on how they were calculated, visit <https://mics.io/uk>.

Project Information

Project timeline: 2012 - 2022
 Project contacts: Izzy Bishop, Steven Loisel
 No. of participants: 3350
 No. of observations: 23844
 Project URL: freshwaterwatch.thewaterhub.org
 Project topic: Water quality monitoring

Rules-based scores

Alquimics are the algorithms behind the MICS platform. They have been created through part handcrafting (a labour-intensive technique for programming that involves writing explicit rules and templates) part machine learning. Handcrafting is the more traditional approach, in which MICS scientists wrote extensive sets of rules to guide the AI's understanding and assessments. The MICS team created five impact domains (environment, economy, governance, science, and society) and wrote assessment-guiding rules for subsets of each of them.

Impact Indicators	Score (max 42)	Discipline average	Overall average
Environment			
Education on environmental challenges	36	28 (8)	24 (12)
Biodiversity loss	38	24 (14)	22 (16)
Science			
Impact through publications	28	32 (+4)	36 (+8)
Science democratisation	25	18 (7)	22 (3)
Economy			
Value for money	18	15 (3)	12 (6)
Commercial opportunities	21	29 (+8)	27 (+6)
Governance			
Policy impact	32	38 (+6)	32 (0)
Ethics and openness	17	21 (+4)	18 (+1)
Society			
Engagement	26	37 (+11)	28 (+2)
Education	31	22 (9)	26 (5)

Value creation

The five levels of value creation of a community:

- Immediate value** - community activities have value in and of themselves.
- Potential value** - activities and interactions can produce "knowledge capital", whose value lies in its potential to be realised later.
- Applied value** - adapting and applying knowledge capital in different contexts can lead to changes or innovations in actions, practice, tools, approaches, or organisational systems.
- Realised value** - not to simply assume that improved performance is the case when people change their practice, but to reflect on what effects the application of knowledge capital is having on the achievement of what matters to stakeholders.
- Reframing value** - a reconsideration of the criteria by which success is defined including reframing strategies, goals, as well as values.

Machine learning scores

For measuring the impact of the overall domains, MICS uses a statistically-driven machine-learning approach (a type of AI that learns to perform a task by analysing patterns in data), which has the computer teach itself to assess impact by learning from data. The machine-learning part of Alquimics is a neural network written in Octave and hosted on Amazon Web Services. Machine learning is a superior method for tackling so-called classification problems, in which neural networks find unifying patterns in noisy data.

Total Score: 34

- Environment: 37
- Science: 26
- Society: 28
- Governance: 24
- Economy: 19

Discipline Average (Environmental studies): 29
 Overall Average: 26

Recommendations

Environment	Education on environmental challenges	Well done! Your score for Environmental Impact is high! In order to maintain this level, keep engagement high through science communication, training events and media posts.
Economy	Value for money	In order to improve the cost efficiency of your project, consider open-source alternatives for software and database solutions.
Governance	Policy impact	To improve the evidence for policy impact of your project, consider publishing results and findings in a policy brief format, as well as scientific publications.

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Figure 12: MICS platform Impact assessment summary report interface

The following table outlines the major elements of the Impact-assessment summary report interface, with a description of the functionality of each.

Table 13: Impact assessment summary report interface elements

Interface Element	Description and function																																																																
<p>Header information</p>	<p>Title, description and logo of the project that has been assessed</p> <p>Project name: Create a project question 1 Project logo: Create a project question 4</p>																																																																
<p>Project information</p>	<p>Information of the project being assessed, as per the project page description. Missing data displayed blank to nudge user to complete.</p> <p>Will make clear if project is active or not.</p> <p>Project timeline: Transition questions Project contacts: Create project question 8 No. Of participants: Transition questions No. Of observations: Transition questions Project URL: Create a project question 10 Project topic: Create a project question 3</p>																																																																
<p>Project map</p>	<p>Maps (x3) of project locations (see 'create a project' process)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project partners • Participants • Observations 																																																																
<p>Rules-based scores</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Impact Indicators</th> <th>Score (max 42)</th> <th>Discipline average</th> <th>Overall average</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Environment</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Education on environmental challenges</td> <td>36</td> <td>28 (6)</td> <td>24 (32)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Biodiversity loss</td> <td>38</td> <td>24 (6)</td> <td>22 (38)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Impact through publications</td> <td>28</td> <td>32 (4)</td> <td>36 (4)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Science democratisation</td> <td>25</td> <td>18 (9)</td> <td>22 (9)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Economy</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Value for money</td> <td>18</td> <td>15 (9)</td> <td>12 (9)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Commercial opportunities</td> <td>21</td> <td>29 (4)</td> <td>27 (4)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Governance</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Policy impact</td> <td>32</td> <td>38 (4)</td> <td>32 (6)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ethics and openness</td> <td>17</td> <td>21 (4)</td> <td>18 (4)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Society</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engagement</td> <td>26</td> <td>37 (2)</td> <td>28 (2)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Education</td> <td>31</td> <td>22 (9)</td> <td>26 (9)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Impact Indicators	Score (max 42)	Discipline average	Overall average	Environment				Education on environmental challenges	36	28 (6)	24 (32)	Biodiversity loss	38	24 (6)	22 (38)	Science				Impact through publications	28	32 (4)	36 (4)	Science democratisation	25	18 (9)	22 (9)	Economy				Value for money	18	15 (9)	12 (9)	Commercial opportunities	21	29 (4)	27 (4)	Governance				Policy impact	32	38 (4)	32 (6)	Ethics and openness	17	21 (4)	18 (4)	Society				Engagement	26	37 (2)	28 (2)	Education	31	22 (9)	26 (9)	<p>Scores per sub-category displayed based on hand-crafted weights from question answers.</p> <p>Includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Score (out of 42) for each sub-category • Average score for the same discipline • Average score overall for all projects on the platform • Colour-coded figures re. difference between project score and averages
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Value creation

A quantitative score representing the value created by the project, based on the Value Creation Network (Guldberg et al., 2019; Wenger et al., 2011). Includes:

- Spiderweb diagram representing the leaning of the project towards the different types of value creation (immediate, potential, applied, realised and reframing)
- A description of each type of value

Machine learning scores

Chart/circles displaying the impact score per domain (as calculated by Alquimics), sized by score, with display of the discipline (topic) and all project averages (on the MICS platform) for comparison

Impact recommendations

Recommendations	Luigi says...
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pollution Reduction Biodiversity Monitoring 	Will done! Your score for Environmental Impact is high! In order to maintain the level, keep engagement high through science communication, training events and media spots.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost Efficiency 	In order to improve the cost efficiency of your project, consider open-source alternatives for software and database solutions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence for Policy 	To improve the evidence for policy impact of your project, consider publishing results and findings in a policy brief format, as well as scientific publications.

A list of curated recommendations per domain, based on the impact scores achieved and the activities of other projects that have scored relatively highly

Data assessment completed and copyright notices

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Display of the data that the assessment was carried out for information, and general creative commons notice with icons

6 Conclusions

This document described the model workflow and rationale for citizen science in impact-evaluation.

This document presented a detailed, technical description of the MICS platform and interfaces for creating a project page, allowing users to represent a citizen-science project on the MICS platform and access the impact assessment framework and tools. This document described the first platform interfaces and elements that a user encounters when accessing the MICS platform, and described them for a first-time user. They represent the first step in the workflow.

This document then presented the next step in the workflow to evaluate the impact of citizen science. It described the development of input features to capture the information required regarding a project's inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts, in order to fully model the impact over five domains. It also described the process of operationalising the input features into questions, presented through three interfaces of the MICS platform so users can access the impact-assessment tools of MICS. This document included a detailed methodological description of how the interface for

capturing data was developed and the elements of one of the main steps in the workflow (entering content-related data).

This document reflected on the current status of the development of the algorithms (called Alquimics). MICS includes two types of algorithms, one based on explicit rules and one on machine learning. These algorithms enter the main workflow when content-related data (input features) are entered. The content-related data are the input of the algorithms. The output of the algorithms are impact scores, which are used in the interface presenting the impact assessment.

Finally, this document presented the visual elements of the impact-assessment report resulting from running Alquimics. The final part of the MICS platform workflow is the output users receive – the reward for their time and effort in setting up a project and supplying the MICS assessment framework with the information required to evaluate impact. The output of the platform is presented to the user through two interfaces: (1) a summary report displayed on screen or downloadable as a pdf, that links to the project page; (2) a full report – giving a detailed breakdown of the impact in each domain, with recommendations to improve.

The main implications of this deliverable for other WPs and tasks in MICS and in future developments are that this document will be used to guide the implementation of the MICS platform in the remaining execution period of the project and potentially after the end of the project, if in the future the MICS platform will be updated or upgraded.

7 References

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MICS - General indicators

A test-bed for potential indicator questions for the MICS project

General questions

Questions leading the user from their project space into the indicator space.

At this point, we understand that you are ready to answer a few (well... a lot of) questions on the xxx project. xxx should be a citizen-science project and you should be the person best positioned to answer questions about the project. If this is not the case, then something went terribly wrong... you can leave this page now and have a good read with "The Science of Citizen Science" book instead (<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-3-030-58278-4>).

Timing is important. Your answers might change as the project evolves. You are always welcome to come back and change them when appropriate. It's very tricky to ask questions that are answerable whatever the development status of the project is, so we assume that the project is currently active. When answering the questions, if the project is no longer active, place yourself in the last month of activity. If the project didn't start yet, place yourself in its first month of activity.

The international community defined ten "principles" of citizen science. You can find them below. Later, the so-called "characteristics" of citizen science have been defined to allow for a more granular definition of the field. You can find them [here]. You can use the principles and the characteristics to warm you up, if you want. But you don't need to. We took them into account and we went deeper, much deeper. Through the MICS platform, you will be able to characterise a project as it has never been possible before. And we will use this characterisation to measure its impact and show the result to you. And to the world.

1

Project's title

Enter your answer

Annex 1 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

2

*(T001) What forms of knowledge does the project (as a whole) create?

- New data
- New analyses
- New written knowledge
- New methodologies
- New concepts
- Other forms of knowledge
- I don't know.

3

*(T002) What is the start date of the project? (It can be in the future. If the project starts with a grant, this is the start date of the funding.)

Please input date (dd/MM/yyyy)

4

*(T003) What is the end date of the project?

Please input date (dd/MM/yyyy)

5

*(T004) The typical duration of a citizen-science project is about 3-4 years. Would that be a decent estimation for this project?

- Yes
- No
- I can't say.

6

*(T005) Are participants currently able to submit data?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 1 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

7

*(T006) How many observations (observations as defined by the project) have been collected so far?

- I know the approximate number.
- I know the order of magnitude.
- I have no idea about how many observations have been collected.
- I don't really know what observations are.
- Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important.

8

*(T007) How many observations are collected in a typical recent year of active project?

- 0 - 300
- 301 - 3000
- More than 3000
- Too difficult to estimate

9

*(TPU008) To put the project's data collection in perspective just think that eBird collected 700 000 000 observations and iNaturalist 40 000 000. We'll tell you more about how your project compares with others in a moment.

- Good to know!
- I don't care...

10

*(T009) How many participants have collected data?

- I know the approximate number.
- I know the order of magnitude.
- I don't know.
- Participants are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important.

Annex 1 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

11

*(T010) How many participants collect data in a typical recent year of active project?

- 0 - 300
- 301 - 3000
- More than 3000
- Too difficult to estimate

12

*(TPU011) On average, in the project, each participant collects [(calculation) observation/participants] observations. In a typical long-tail situation, 10% of the participants would collect [(calculation to be defined) x] observations, and 90% would collect [(calculation to be defined) y] observations.

- Good to know!
- I don't care...

13

*(T012) Including participants who collect data, how many people have been engaged by the project (excluding social media)?

We will ask you more about "spin off" projects in future questions

- 0 - 300
- 301 - 3000
- 3001 - 30,000
- 30,001 - 300,000
- More than 300,000
- I don't know.

14

*(T013) Could you quantify the total funding received by the project (in £, € or \$) (for example, "2 000 000")?

The value must be a number

Annex 1 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

15

*(T014) How is news about the project published?

- Mostly text
- Mostly oral
- Mostly visual (images, infographics)
- Mostly video
- Unknown
- Other

16

Pop-up: Some projects experiment with rich, multimedia formats. Turns out consumers like news in text form, thank you very much. Simply put, video takes too long.) (Wired, Mar 2018)

- Good to know!
- I don't care...

17

*(GG065) Is the project focused on one or more of the following five domains?

- Economy: the production and exchange of goods and services among economic agents
- Environment: the bio-chemical-physical environment
- Governance: the processes and institutions through which decisions are made, both informal and formal
- Science and technology: the scientific process (method) as well as research more broadly; the scientific system, scientific paradigms and resulting technological artefacts and standards
- Society: individuals as well as collective (societal) values, understanding, actions and well-being (including relationships)

Submit

MICS - Society indicators

A test-bed for potential indicator questions for the MICS project

Society domain

Questions focussed on the impact of citizen science on society

1

Project's title

Enter your answer

2

*(SG016) Who co-ordinates the project?

- Professionals (paid to work on the project)
- Citizens (as defined by citizen science, not by citizenship)
- An AI :-)
- Some other kind of actor
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

3

*(SG017) What type of organisation leads the project?

- Public bodies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Commercial organisations
- Research-performing organisations (including universities)
- Some other kind of organisation
- I don't know.

4

*(SG018) What type of organisations are associated with the project?

- Public bodies
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Commercial organisations
- Research-performing organisations
- Some other kind of organisation
- I don't know.

5

*(SA021) Does the project have a code of ethics available to the participant?

- Yes
- No (Pop-up: here's an example you can use)
- I don't know.

6

*(SA022) Does the project have explicit health and safety regulations in place?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

7

*(SA023) Does the project involve the collection of personal data of the participants? (Personal data is any information that relates to an identified, or identifiable, living individual.)

- Yes, at least sometimes
- No
- I don't know.

8

*(SA024) Is payment required by the participants to take part in the project?

- Yes, at least in some cases
- No
- I don't know.

9

*(SA025) What is this payment used for?

- Equipment/services given to the participants
- General support to an organisation
- Training given to the participants
- Something else
- I don't know.

10

*(SH026) Are participants the object/focus of the research? (This might be the case, for example, in health and medical research.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

11

*(SH027) Does the project investigate human health?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

12

*(SH028) Does the project explicitly aid in fighting communicable diseases? (This paper provides an example of the context that can help to understand the question: "A Global Digital Citizen Science Policy to Tackle Pandemics Like COVID-19" [<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7284491/>].)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

13

*(SH029) Does the project investigate diseases (such as, for example, cardiovascular, cancer, diabetes or respiratory)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

14

*(SH030) Does the project contribute to the research and development of vaccines or medicines?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

15

*(SH031) Does the project directly address mental health concerns? (This paper provides an example of the context that can help to understand the question: "Developing a Citizen Social Science approach to understand urban stress and promote wellbeing in urban communities" [<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-020-0460-1>].)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

16

*(SP032) What is the degree of participation of the citizen scientists, according to the following categories?

- Contractual projects, where communities ask professional researchers to conduct a specific scientific investigation and report on the results
- Contributory projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public primarily contribute data
- Collaborative projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public contribute data but also help to refine project design, analyse data, or disseminate findings
- Co-created projects, which are designed by scientists and members of the public working together and for which at least some of the public participants are actively involved in most aspects of the research process
- Collegial projects, where non-credentialed individuals conduct research independently with varying degrees of expected recognition by institutionalised science or professionals
- The project doesn't fit any of these categories. (Jennifer won't be happy.)
- I don't know.

17

*(SP033) In which phases of the project do participants play a role?

- Identifying a research question
- Definition of project activities
- Collecting data
- Analysing data
- Monitoring in ways other than collecting data
- Training other participants
- Publication of outputs
- Assessment of project impacts
- Closure or handover of the project
- Something else
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

18

(SP034) Are participants aware they are contributing to a research project and have they actively chosen to be involved in the project?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

19

*(SP035) Are the options for participation and the degree of involvement diversified?

- Yes
- No: participants have only one option of involvement.
- I don't know.

20

*(SP036) Are participants and other stakeholders (usually, scientists) equal partners in the knowledge generation process (that is, the conclusions drawn from the data)?

- Yes
- No; participants dominate the knowledge generation. (This is very unlikely. Please, double check before selecting it.)
- No; another stakeholder dominates the knowledge generation.
- I don't know.

21

*(SP037) How is the involvement of participants formally recognised in publications?

- Individual authorship
- Group pseudonym as (co-)author
- Individuals acknowledged by name
- Group of participants collectively acknowledged
- Participants are not formally recognised in publications
- The project does not have any publications yet
- I don't know.

22

*(SE038) What is the balance between engagement and research in the project?

- More engagement
- More research
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

23

*(SE039) What engagement strategies does the project have?

- Gamification
- Real-time validation on observation/data submission
- Notification of updates to contributed observations
- Tips of the day
- Personalised recommendations
- Feedback on data quality
- Active and responsive social-media presence ("responsive" in the sense that questions from participants are responded)
- Storytelling or exchanging of experiences
- Invitation to or suggestion of events
- Workshops
- Measurement campaigns
- Active and responsive pilot presence ("responsive" in the sense that questions from participants are responded)
- A forum, or other platform on a website
- Awareness raising (ad-hoc demonstrations, meetings, and appearances from partners)
- Photo contests
- Social events not included in previous options
- Creation of champions, ambassadors or leaders
- Organic conversation
- Other strategies

24

*(SE040) Is the engagement strategy clearly and transparently communicated to participants?

- Yes
- No
- The project doesn't have a formal engagement strategy.
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

25

*(SE041) How much involvement and responsibility are offered to the participants? (with options depending on interests, availability and knowledge).

- A lot of involvement and responsibility
- A lot of involvement but not much responsibility
- Not much involvement but a lot responsibility
- Not much involvement or responsibility
- I don't know.

26

*(SE042) We understand that participants are motivated to engage in project activities. Are they also motivated to get involved in similar activities outside of the project?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

27

*(SC043) We understand that the project carries out communication activities; but does the project have specific communication plans for specific target groups?

- Yes
- No
- The project has only one target group.
- I don't know.

28

*(SC045) If the project has an explicit outreach or communication strategy, which of the following elements does it include?

- Hands-on experiences (for example, an interactive exhibit)
- Multi-directional communication (for example, a forum where all stakeholders can have a voice)
- Innovative means of science communication (for example, via TikTok)
- Collaboration with science-communication professionals
- Other outreach and communication approaches
- The project does not have an outreach or communication strategy
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

29

*(SC046) Which channels does the project use to communicate with participants?

- In person
- In print
- Online social media (blogs)
- Online social media (microblogs: for example, Twitter)
- Online social media (social and professional networks: for example, Facebook, LinkedIn)
- Online social media (fora, for example [EU-Citizen.Science \(https://eu-citizen.science/forum/\)](https://eu-citizen.science/forum/))
- Online social media (image and video-sharing platforms: for example, YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, Pinterest)
- Online media (newsletter)
- Online media (webpage)
- Other channels
- I don't know

30

*(SC044) How are the objectives and results of the project communicated or shared?

	Objectives	Data and results	Objectives, data and results
Formal scholarly outputs: e.g. peer-review publications, open data sets, abstracts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Internally produced outputs: e.g. newsletters, leaflets, blog posts, social media posts, podcasts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Externally produced outputs: e.g. magazine or newspaper articles, TV or radio interviews	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Events: e.g. lectures, workshops, fairs, seminars or webinars	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other ways	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

31

*(SC048) Are there plans for sustaining the collaboration between citizen scientists and other stakeholders (for example, scientists or public authorities) after the end of the project-coordination support?

- Yes
- No
- There is no collaboration between citizens and other stakeholders (for example, scientists or public authorities) in the project.
- There are no plans to end the project-coordination support
- I don't know.

32

*(SE049) What kind of specific training does the project provide to participants? (We will ask you about more general education later)

- IT training (for example, using a website)
- Equipment training (for example, using an app)
- Measurement training
- Train the trainer
- Training about citizen-science methodologies
- Some other kind of training
- I don't know.

33

*(SE050) If the project involves educating participants, what education does it provide?

- Primary-level education to pupils
- Secondary-level education to pupils (middle and high school)
- Adult education or life-long learning
- Other education
- The project does not involve educating participants
- I don't know

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

34

*(SE051) Does the project work with educational institutions to make sustainable development part of the curricula?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

35

*(SE052) What are the learning outcomes for individuals (in terms of new knowledge, skills or competencies)?

- New knowledge
- New skills (specific learned activities)
- New competencies (on-the-job behaviors which often require specific skills and knowledge)
- Other learning outcomes
- I don't know.

36

*(SE053) Does the project ease access to traditional and local knowledge resources?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

37

*(SI054) Are support and training adapted to the different participant groups (e.g. participants age, language)?

- Yes, at least in part.
- No
- The project has only one participant type.
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

38

*(SI055) Does the project explicitly promote the inclusion of all people (for example, people from ethnic minorities)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

39

*(SI056) Has the project been designed to give access to all participants, including those with functional diversity [[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_diversity_\(disability\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_diversity_(disability))]?

- Yes
- No
- It's not possible. (For example, it could be impossible to collect data along a river on a wheelchair, and that's the only thing participants can do.)
- I don't know.

40

*(SI057) Does the project explicitly contribute to gender equality?

- Yes, at the decision-making level
- Yes, at other levels
- No
- I don't know.

41

*(SI058) Does the project actively engage participants from disadvantaged backgrounds?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

42

*(SI059) Does the project actively raise motivation or self-esteem amongst participants?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

43

*(SS060) Does the project contribute to social innovation?

(Social innovation is the process of developing and deploying effective solutions to challenging and often systemic social and environmental issues in support of social progress. These solutions often require the active collaboration of constituents across government, business, and the nonprofit world.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

44

*(SS061) Does the project foster resilience, or does it foster learning and adaptation (which then leads to resilience)?

This is often done by fostering one of the following:
(1) the will and intention to maintain social-ecological resilience
(2) knowledge about the problem and the desired direction of change
(3) proactive behaviour
(4) the capacity to change existing patterns of behaviour.

- Yes
- No
- After five minutes, I still don't understand the question.
- I don't know.

45

*(SS062) Does the project foster social capital? (Social capital is the networks of relationships among people that enable society to function effectively.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

46

*(SS063) Does the project contribute to personal change in behaviour (for example, "switching from plastic bags to reusable shopping bags" or "changing an omnivorous diet to a vegan one and losing all friends in the process")?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

47

(SDG Pop up) The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. At its heart are the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

- (1) No Poverty
- (2) Zero Hunger
- (3) Good Health and Well-being
- (4) Quality Education
- (5) Gender Equality
- (6) Clean Water and Sanitation
- (7) Affordable and Clean Energy
- (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth
- (9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
- (10) Reducing Inequality
- (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities
- (12) Responsible Consumption and Production
- (13) Climate Action
- (14) Life Below Water
- (15) Life On Land
- (16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions
- (17) Partnerships for the Goals

Citizen science is an emerging example of a non-traditional data source that is making a contribution to measuring these goals.

- Good to know!
- I don't care...

Annex 2 Society input feature Microsoft Forms

48

*(SG019) Which socially-relevant issues - as represented by the SDGs - are directly addressed by the project?

(We ask about other SDGs, for example, the ones related to the environment, somewhere else; don't worry.)

- No poverty
- Zero hunger
- Good health and well-being
- Quality education
- Gender equality
- Decent work and economic growth
- Reduced inequalities
- Responsible consumption and production
- Peace, justice and strong institutions

49

*(SG020) Does the project explicitly support effective and targeted capacity-building related to national plans to implement SDGs?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

50

Finally, what is the meaning of citizen science, life, the universe, and everything?

- 42
- Are you asking me to define citizen science, because I'm not opening that can of worms
- I don't know, but I'm glad this is over

Submit

Annex 3 Governance input feature Microsoft Forms

MICS - Governance indicators

A test-bed for potential indicator questions for the MICS project

Governance domain

Questions focussed on impact on governance

1

Project's title

2

(GG066) Does the project contribute data to a country's official reporting for a Sustainable Development Goal indicator?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

3

(GG067) Does the project engage multiple stakeholders to share knowledge in relation to the achievement of the SDGs?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 3 Governance input feature Microsoft Forms

4

(GA068) Are the data generated by the project open access?

- Data can be shared
- Data can be edited or combined with other material to produce a new work
- Data can be used for commercial purposes
- Data can be used without attribution to the author
- No
- I don't know.

5

(GA069) Does the project explicitly state which ethical procedures it follows to ensure the data are collected and processed lawfully? (See, for example [\[mics.tools/.../Ethics](#) requirements: Protection of personal data])

- Yes
- No
- The project is not about data collection, and doesn't collect or process personal data.
- The project doesn't need to ensure the data are collected lawfully.
- I don't know.

6

(GA070) Does the project include opportunities for project leaders and participants to discuss the ethical and political dimensions of the research carried out?

- Yes
- No
- The research element of the project is not significant.
- I don't know.

7

(GA071) Do citizens know what the data collected by the project are used for?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 3 Governance input feature Microsoft Forms

8

(GA160) Do citizens know where the data collected by the project are stored?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

9

(GA161) Do citizens know whether the data collected by the project are shared?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

10

(GA072) Are data access rights clear and transparent?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

11

(GA073) Do participants have to explicitly give consent (for example, signing a consent form) to take part in the project? (See, for example [\[mics.tools/.../Ethics requirements: Participant informed-consent procedures\]](#))

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

12

(GP074) Does the project explicitly foster ownership of the project amongst participants?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 3 Governance input feature Microsoft Forms

13

(GP076) Does the project make sure that those with less power, women, and minorities are among those who are asking the questions?

- Yes
- No or not yet
- I don't know.

14

(Pop up) Whether the scientific questions to be addressed by a citizen science project come from citizens themselves or civic educators - including scientists, professional researchers, and their institutions - needs to be interrogated.

Is it reasonable to expect communities to ask the questions?

Is it overambitious to assume that they can?

Does suggesting that they cannot indicate a level of institutional and structural racism?

Empowering people includes enabling them to drive citizen-science projects. (Ceccaroni et al., 2021)

- Good to know!
- I don't care...

15

(GC077) Does the project explicitly foster new collaborations amongst different societal actors and groups (not including those between citizens and scientists)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

16

(GC078) Does the project work with other organisations to involve specific target groups or individuals (for example, a river trust for water-quality monitoring or a local community action group)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 3 Governance input feature Microsoft Forms

17

(GC079) Does the project collaborate with other initiatives to enhance mutual learning?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

18

(GC080) Which resources does the project share with other initiatives?

- Data
- Learnings
- Participants
- Instruments (for example, measuring kits)
- Methodologies
- Resources on the theory and practice of citizen science
- Communication channels
- Other resources
- I don't know.

19

(GC081) The following question refers to "institutional change". You can consider institutions broadly as "a system of rules, beliefs, norms and organizations that together generate a regularity of (social) behaviour".

The institutional change is usually measured along the following six dimensions:

1. Open access/data
2. Ethics
3. Gender equality
4. Public engagement
5. Science education
6. Responsible research and innovation

Based on these 'dimensions', what institutional change does the project contribute to?

- Ethics: for example, creation of an ethics board or employment of a quality assurance officer
- Open access/data: for example, development of an organisational Data Management Plan
- Public engagement: for example, specialists interacting with non-specialists
- Science education: for example, teaching and learning of science to non-scientists
- Gender equality: for example, development of a Gender Equality Plan
- Responsible research and innovation: for example, development of practices that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness or sustainability of research and innovation processes and products
- Other institutional changes
- I don't know.

Annex 3 Governance input feature Microsoft Forms

20

(GC082) Does the project have any explicit impact on external organisational policy (for example, the Outfall Safari project causing a change in the policies of Thames Water)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

21

(GC083) Does the project explicitly inform any governmental policy process?

- Yes, at the sub-national level
- Yes, at the national level
- Yes, at the international level
- No
- I don't know.

Submit

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

MICS - Economy indicators

A test-bed for potential indicator questions for the MICS project

Economy domain

Questions focussed on the impact on the economy

1

Project's title

Enter your answer

2

*(EP084) How is or was the project funded?

- European Union (for example, via Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe)
- Other international sponsors
- US National Science Foundation
- NASA
- Other US federal sponsors
- Other national sponsors
- Crowdfunding

Micro funding (There is a general connection between all forms of alternative funding: they all provide access to capital for a segment of the population that cannot access it through traditional means. However, there are significant differences between micro funding and crowdfunding. Micro funding includes microfinance and social (peer-to-peer) lending, and is not commonly used in citizen science. Microfinance provides loans and other basic financial services to the poor. Social lending gives ordinary people the ability to lend around the world.)

- Corporate sponsors
- Non-governmental organisations
- Internal funding of the coordinating organisation
- Other funding sources
- I don't know.

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

3

*(EP085) Is participation in the project voluntary or non-voluntary?

- Voluntary
- Non-voluntary (for example, pupils who have to participate as part of school activities)
- Both
- I don't know.

4

*(EP086) Does the project involve a socio-economically diverse pool of participants?

- Yes
- No; participants are from the same socio-economical group.
- I don't know.

5

*(EP087) Does the project offer any tangible incentives for participation?

- Merchandise
- Vouchers
- General equipment, such as bird-boxes
- Access to media and special events
- Scientific equipment, such as sensors
- Co-authorship
- Socialisation
- A good excuse to avoid lockdown restrictions
- Other
- I don't know.

6

*(EP088) Can participants make a voluntary financial contribution to the project?

- Yes (For example, Patreon supporter)
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

7

*(EP089) How much time is invested by scientists in engaging and training citizens?

- Scientists don't engage and train citizens.
- Not much (hours)
- Some (days)
- A lot (there are one or more people, or a work package, explicitly dedicated to engaging and training citizens)
- Too difficult to quantify
- I don't know.

8

*(EC090) Does the project have explicit links with public authorities (for example, having them as partners of the consortium managing the project)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

9

*(EC091) Does the project involve commercial activities related to industry or academia?

- Yes (for example, commercialisation of sensors developed within the project)
- No
- I don't know.

10

(EC092) Does the project include any competitive advantage (on the economic, rather than the scientific scale)?

Here "competitive advantage" refers to factors that allow an organisation to produce outputs or services better or more cheaply than its rivals.

For example, incorporation of citizen science might provide a competitive advantage for the ecotourism providers in the tourism market

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

11

*(EC093) Does the project explicitly promote the formation and growth of micro-, small- or medium-sized enterprises?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

12

*(EC094) Does the project promote sustainable tourism?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

13

*(ET095) What technology does the project use or develop?

	Uses a pre-existing version	Develops a new version	Both
Apps	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sensors	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Platforms	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Digital solutions (digitalising old methodologies, processes or technology)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other technologies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We don't use technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

14

*(ET096) Does the project require recurring investments in technology (for example, software licences or app/platform maintenance) that affect its long-term sustainability?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

15

*(ET097) Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

16

*(ET098) Does the project explicitly promote the development, transfer or dissemination of environmentally-sound technologies (documented, for example, in a dissemination plan)?

Environmentally sound technologies are techniques and technologies capable of reducing environmental damage through processes and materials that generate fewer potentially damaging substances, recover such substances from emissions prior to discharge, or utilize and recycle production residues.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

17

*(EE099) Does the project have an explicit sustainability plan?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

18

*(EE100) Does the project collaborate with external companies to enable the adoption of sustainable practices?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

19

*(EE101) Does the project have any concrete cooperation in place for the exploitation of results; i.e. the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

20

*(EE102) Does the project have any economic potential to be exploited in the future (for example, new intellectual property with economic value, or new sensors with a clear market, or the prospect to employ new personnel)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

21

*(EE103) Did the project generate related new projects or new project proposals?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

22

*(EE104) Does the project explicitly contribute to the reduction of government expenditure?

"Not yet, but it might one day?" Don't worry, you can always come back and update your answers on the MICS platform when it does.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

23

*(EC105) If it has been estimated, how does the project compare, from a purely economical point of view, with using experts or traditional scientific methods?

- It has not been estimated.
- It has been estimated and there is no clear winner from the purely economic point of view.
- Citizen science clearly produces savings in comparison with using experts or traditional scientific methods.
- We know that you will never admit that citizen science is more expensive or less efficient than traditional methods, but here is the option; just in case.
- I don't know.

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

23

*(EC105) If it has been estimated, how does the project compare, from a purely economical point of view, with using experts or traditional scientific methods?

- It has not been estimated.
- It has been estimated and there is no clear winner from the purely economic point of view.
- Citizen science clearly produces savings in comparison with using experts or traditional scientific methods.
- We know that you will never admit that citizen science is more expensive or less efficient than traditional methods, but here is the option; just in case.
- I don't know.

24

*(EC106) How many hours, on average, does a participant dedicate to the project in a typical recent year? We acknowledge that this can vary hugely from participant to participant; go with an average participant.

- Less than 3
- 3-30
- More than 30
- The project has no participants.
- I don't know.

25

*(EC107) By using citizen scientists (rather than professionals) is the project able to cover a larger sample size (i.e., to collect or analyse a larger amount of data)?

- Yes
- No
- Not relevant for the project
- Too difficult to say
- I don't know.

26

*(EC108) What are the estimated, typical, annual personnel costs across the project (in £, € or \$)?

- Less than 30,000
- 30,000-300,000
- More than 300,000
- I don't know.

Annex 4 Economy input feature Microsoft Forms

27

*(EC109) Excluding personnel costs, what is the estimated, approximate cost per observation (in £, € or \$) (observations as defined by the project)?

- Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying their cost is not important.
- Less than 2 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.)
- 2-8 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of three sevenths of the world population.)
- 9-32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of two sevenths of the world population.)
- More than 32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.)
- I don't know.

28

*(EC110) What are the estimated, typical, annual costs of IT systems for data collection and management (in £, € or \$) (for example for the use of Amazon Web Services or other cloud computing services)?

- Less than 300
- 300-3000
- 3001-30,000
- More than 30,000
- I don't know.

29

*(EC112) On a scale of 1 to 3 (1 being "not at all" and 3 being "very well"), how would you score the ability of the data collected in the project to answer the question posed at the start of the project?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- The project does not collect data
- Not relevant to the project
- I don't know

Submit

Annex 5 Environment input feature Microsoft Forms

MICS - Environment indicators

A test-bed for potential indicator questions for the MICS project

Environment domain

Questions focussed towards impact on the environment

1

Project's title

Enter your answer

2

(SDG Pop up) The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. At its heart are the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

- (1) No Poverty
- (2) Zero Hunger
- (3) Good Health and Well-being
- (4) Quality Education
- (5) Gender Equality
- (6) Clean Water and Sanitation
- (7) Affordable and Clean Energy
- (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth
- (9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
- (10) Reducing Inequality
- (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities
- (12) Responsible Consumption and Production
- (13) Climate Action
- (14) Life Below Water
- (15) Life On Land
- (16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions
- (17) Partnerships for the Goals

Citizen science is an emerging example of a non-traditional data source that is making a contribution to measuring these goals.

Good to know!

I don't care...

Annex 5 Environment input feature Microsoft Forms

3

(ES113) Which environmental issues - as represented by the SDG)- are related to the aims of the project? (We'll ask details about each issue later.)

- Zero hunger (including sustainable agriculture)
- Clean water and sanitation (freshwater not marine)
- Affordable and clean energy
- Sustainable cities and communities (including urban air quality)
- Responsible consumption and production (including food waste and chemical pollution)
- Climate action
- Life below water (marine not freshwater)
- Life on land
- Other environmental issues

4

(ES114) How does the project contribute to sustainable agriculture?

- Increasing the proportion of agricultural area being managed sustainably
- Increasing investment in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and technology development
- Researching sustainable agriculture
- Other activities related to sustainable agriculture

5

(ES115) Does the project contribute to secure plant and animal genetic resources in either medium- or long-term conservation facilities?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

6

(ES116) Does the project explicitly investigate the link between pollution and health?

- Yes, air pollution
- Yes, water pollution
- Yes, some other kind of pollution
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 5 Environment input feature Microsoft Forms

7

(ES117) With regards to clean water and sanitation, which of the following activities does the project include?

	Monitors	Has a measurable impact on	Both monitors and has a measurable impact on
Ambient water quality/pollution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water-related ecosystems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Involving local communities in water management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water-use efficiency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Water stress or water scarcity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Correct treatment of wastewater	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other activities related to clean water and sanitation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8

(ES118) How does the project contribute to affordable and clean energy? (Clean energy includes sources like sunlight, wind, rain, tides, waves, and geothermal heat.)

- Increasing the share of clean energy in the energy mix
- Increasing energy efficiency
- Researching clean energy
- Other activities related to clean energy

9

(ES119) With regards to clean air and sustainable cities, which of the following activities does the project include?

	Monitors	Has a measurable impact on	Both monitors and has a measurable impact on
Involving local communities in urban planning and management	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Correct collection and treatment of solid waste	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ambient air quality/pollution (including fine particulate matter e.g. PM2.5 and PM10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Green public spaces	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other activities related to sustainable cities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Annex 5 Environment input feature Microsoft Forms

10

(ES120) With regards to responsible production and consumption, which of the following activities does the project include?

	Monitors	Has a measurable impact on	Both monitors and has a measurable impact on
Food waste	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Harmful chemicals in the air	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Harmful chemicals in the water	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Harmful chemicals in the soil	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Waste generation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other activities related to responsible consumption and production	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11

(ES121) Does the project explicitly disseminate information on sustainable development or lifestyles?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

12

(ES122) Does the project educate participants on environmental challenges?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

13

(ES123) With regards to life below water (marine not freshwater), which of the following activities does the project include?

	Monitors	Has a measurable impact on	Both monitors and has a measurable impact on
Marine nutrient pollution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine plastic pollution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ocean acidification	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine protected areas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Marine technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other activities related to life below water (marine not freshwater)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Annex 5 Environment input feature Microsoft Forms

14

(ES124) With regards to life on land, which of the following activities does the project include?

	Monitors	Has a measurable impact on	Both monitors and has a measurable impact on
Sustainable management of forests	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Desertification or land degradation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mountain ecosystems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other terrestrial ecosystems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Biodiversity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Species extinction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Invasive alien species	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wildlife poaching or trafficking	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other activities related to life on land	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15

(EG125) Does the project include objectives to protect or enhance natural resources?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

16

(EG126) Does the project explicitly contribute to a higher awareness of, or responsibility for, the natural environment, on this planet or others?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Submit

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

MICS - Science indicators

A test-bed for potential indicator questions for the MICS project

Science domain

Questions focussed towards impact on science

1

Project's title

Enter your answer

2

*(SG127) Which disciplines are involved in the project?

- Citizen science (If you don't select this one, you are in trouble.)
- Agricultural and veterinary sciences (including, forestry sciences, fisheries sciences, and land and farm management)
- Art theory and criticism
- Biological sciences (including ecology, zoology, genetics, and biodiversity)
- Chemical sciences (including medicinal and biomolecular chemistry)
- Earth sciences (including geology, atmospheric sciences, and oceanography)
- Engineering (including food sciences, environmental engineering, and biomedical engineering)
- Environmental sciences (including ecological applications, environmental management, and soil sciences)
- Information and computing sciences (including artificial intelligence and image processing, distributed computing, and computer software)
- Language, communication and culture (including linguistics, and literary studies)
- Law and legal studies
- Mathematical sciences and statistics
- Medical and health sciences (including neurosciences, public health and health services, nutrition and dietetics, and human movement and sports science)
- Philosophy and religious studies (including applied ethics, and history and philosophy of specific fields)
- Physical sciences (including astronomical and space sciences, atomic, molecular, nuclear, particle and plasma physics, and quantum physics)
- Psychology and cognitive sciences
- Studies in human society (including human geography, policy and administration, sociology, and education)
- Technology (including communications technologies, and computer hardware)
- I don't know.
- Something else (Really?!)

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

3

*(SG128) What is the scope of the research? (The project, for example, studies plastic pollution worldwide.)

- Local
- Regional
- National
- International
- Global
- Galactic
- I don't know.

4

*(SG129) Is the project's citizen science basic or applied?

Basic science, such as understanding how cells work, is research aimed at understanding fundamental problems. Applied science, such as the medical field, is the application of basic scientific knowledge to solve practical problems.

- Basic
- Applied
- Both
- Too difficult to distinguish
- I don't know.

5

*(SG130) Is the project's research inductive or deductive?

Inductive reasoning is described as a method where one's experiences and observations are synthesised to come up with a general truth. Many dictionaries define inductive reasoning as deriving general principles from specific observations: "bottom-up logic".

Deductive reasoning, or "top-down logic", is the process of reasoning from one or more statements (premises) to reach a logical conclusion.

- Inductive
- Deductive
- Both
- I don't know.

6

*(SG131) Do participants take part in systematic or convenience data-collection?

Convenience data-collection or sampling - also known as grab sampling, accidental sampling, or opportunity sampling - is a type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. This type of sampling is the most common in citizen science.

- Systematic data-collection (for example, data collected from a vessel along a transect)
- Convenience data-collection (for example, data collected from a vessel of opportunity like a ferry)
- Both
- Data collection is not a significant element of the project.
- I don't know.

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

7

*(SD132) The following four questions focus on the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'.

Are the data generated by the project findable?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

8

*(SD133) Are the data generated by the project accessible?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

9

*(SD134) Are the data generated by the project interoperable?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

10

*(SD135) Are the data generated by the project reusable?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

11

*(SD136) What processes are defined in the project to guarantee high data-quality?

- Data profiling - Initially assessing the data to understand their current state, often including value distributions
- Data standardization - Ensuring that data conform to standards
- Matching or linking - A way to compare data so that similar but slightly different records can be aligned; matching may use "fuzzy logic" to find duplicates in the data; it can for example recognise that "Sasha Wood" and "Sasha Woods" may be the same individual.
- Data monitoring - Keeping track of data quality over time and reporting variations in the quality of data
- Peer-to-peer validation - More-expert participants validating observations by less-expert participants
- Expert validation - professionals validating observations by participants
- Artificial intelligence - For example, improving image or audio classification by using computer vision or computer hearing
- Other processes
- I don't know.

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

12

*(SD137) Does the project link participants to experts (for example, to validate data)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

13

*(SD138) Does the project have or adopt a code of research or a research integrity policy available to participants? (See, for example [<https://ukrio.org/publications/code-of-practice-for-research/>])

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

14

*(SK139) Does the project investigate the social or psychological needs of animals?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

15

*(SK140) Does the project contribute to a better understanding of science?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

16

*(SK141) Does the project formally build on existing citizen-science expertise in the specific field of research?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

17

*(SK142) Is new knowledge developed regarding how best to incorporate citizens into research design?

- Yes, and formally documented
- Yes, but not formally documented
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

18

*(EC111) How many open-access publications, indexed by Google Scholar, resulted from the project?

- Less than 3
- 3-30
- More than 30
- I don't know.

19

*(SK143) How many citations have the publications produced by the project received, in total (according to Google scholar)?

- Less than 3
- 3-30
- 31-300
- More than 300
- I don't know.

20

*(SK144) What is the highest impact-factor (or impact-index) of the publications produced by the project? (Just Google: "[journal name]" impact factor)

- Less than 2
- 2-5
- More than 5
- I don't know.

21

*(ST145) Does the project use mobile phones as a primary tool (for example, using an app to collect observations)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

22

*(ST146) Is participation possible without a phone connected to the internet?

- No; it's nearly impossible.
- Yes; participation is possible without a phone, but a computer connected to the internet is necessary.
- Yes; participation is possible without a phone or a computer connected to the internet.
- I don't know.

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

23

*(ST147) Does the project provide technical support to participants?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

24

*(ST148) Does the project use enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

25

*(ST149) Does the project enhance international cooperation on science, technology or innovation?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

26

*(SP150) Are participants exposed to steps in the scientific process in a systematic manner?

For example, are they presented with the problem before they are presented with the method?
Are they exposed to the results before they are given the conclusion.

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

27

*(SP151) Are participants able to challenge the project's methodologies?

- Yes, and this could result in methodologies changing
- Yes, but this could not result in methodologies changing (because, for example, data need to be compared with existing datasets or because some SDG indicator is determining the parameters to measure, even if they don't necessarily make sense in a particular location)
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

28

*(SP152) Does the project provide participants with easy and explicit access to pertinent research findings or salient literature used to inform the project before research begins?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

29

*(SP153) Does the project have a formal dissemination strategy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

30

*(SP154) Does the project influence the attitudes of participants regarding science (hopefully in a positive way)?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

31

*(SP155) Are participants explicitly encouraged to reflect on or discuss current values, perspectives, opinions and attitudes relating to general science concepts?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

32

*(SP156) Do changes in participants' values, perspectives, opinions and attitudes occur as a consequence of actions carried out in the project?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Annex 6 Science input feature Microsoft Forms

33

*(SP157) Are participants explicitly exposed to various careers in science through the project?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

34

*(SP158) Are project leaders challenged to consider novel connections between their own careers and research, and the context of participating citizens?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

35

*(SP159) Has adequate consideration been given to allow citizen participants time and space to participate in the research given other demands and responsibilities?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know.

Submit

Annex 7 Input feature interview guide

Welcome & introduction (5 minutes)

(Re-)introduction to MICS.

- MICS is interested, not just in measuring the impact of the project but also characterising the project and providing useful feedback on how they can change and improve their project.

Context

- We have prepared a series of questions which we'd like to receive your feedback on.
- They are not the final set of MICS questions and there might be things which are missing.
- The questions are in Microsoft Forms. The interface on the MICS platform will be very different. You can provide comments on the questions as you see them, including how easy or difficult it is to answer them in the Forms but we will try and flag anything which we know will change in the platform.
- The indicators are not bound to a single domain.
- Almost everything is pre-defined. There are no free-text fields. But we are still building the answers, so if you select Other, we'll ask you for more details which we will use to improve our choice of answers going forward.
- People will not have to answer the questions in one go as we are doing today.

Purpose of the interview:

- To test the relevance and usability of the questions so that we can refine them before implementing them in a platform.
- To collect detailed data about each project to form the basis of an initial database for the MICS platform.

Practicalities:

- There are six questionnaires in Microsoft forms with a total of around 150 questions.
- We will go through each question together and you just have to answer it in the form.
- As you do, we might ask questions about how you're finding it, but please also give feedback on each question if you have anything to say.
- At the end of each questionnaire, we'll ask a few additional questions and there will be a short wrap-up at the end of all the forms.
- The interview is likely to take around five hours. We'll offer regular opportunities for breaks but feel free to request a short break whenever you want.
- (if an EU project) here is the Cordis link for your project which may be helpful for some of the basic questions.
- If during the interview you need to check anything please let us know what you're looking at e.g. Cordis, google scholar, project reports, so that we can use it to help future users answer the questions.

What MICS will do with the obtained information:

- From these interviews and other activities, MICS will test and refine this set of questions which can then be implemented on the MICS platform.

Annex 7 Input feature interview guide

- The data collected on your project will also help us to develop the output of the MICS platform including how we describe the impact of each project.

All project data will be open access. All personal data, including pizza preferences and address will be strictly confidential.

[Make sure you have received a signed copy of the MICS Informed Consent sheet from the interviewee.]

Question prompts

- Does the question feel relevant to your project?
- Is the question easy to understand?
 - Do you need further information to answer the question?
 - Would more examples or prompts be helpful?
- Are any answer options missing in the question? If you selected “Other” what would your answer be in a free-text field?
- Are you able to answer the question with the information you have currently available or would you need to look things up or ask other people?
- Is there any way you can think of to improve the question?

SDGs:

- If you are monitoring an indicator, are you using the parameters required for the indicator
 - Do you know what they are?
- If not, why not? What could be done to allow you? Lack of knowledge? No capacity?
- How did you choose the parameters that you are measuring?

Section prompts

- Did any questions seem out of place or not relevant either to the domain or to the impact of your project?
- Did you find any questions particularly enjoyable, interesting or thought provoking?
- Did the order of the questions make sense?
- Are you surprised that we didn’t ask a particular question in this domain?

Wrap-up questions

- Follow up question to GG065 in general questions:
 - How would you rank the relative impact of the project in each of the five domains?
 - Can you score the project’s impact as “high” or “low” in each of these domains?
- How did you find the experience of answering all the questions?
- How do you think the experience would have been different if we weren’t together in a call? Would it have been easier or harder?
- Are you surprised that we didn’t ask a particular question? Is there anything missing in the 150 questions?
- Do you feel we could effectively characterise your project with the information collected in the questionnaires?
- Do you feel we could effectively measure the impact of your project with the information collected in the questionnaires?

Annex 7 Input feature interview guide

Closing

Those are all the questions that we wanted to ask. Thank you for your time!

Explanation of the next steps

- All results from interviews will be analysed.
- The questions will be refined before being implemented in an online toolbox for citizen science projects to measure the (evolving) impacts of their project/initiative
- We will invite you to test the tools and give feedback

If these questions are implemented in the MICS platform, we'll offer to enter all the information you've provided today so that you don't have to refill all the questions.

We will write a paper and invite you to be authors.

We can now share some mock-ups of the project platform if interested.

Annex 8 General input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
What forms of knowledge does the project as a whole create?	New data (quantitative or qualitative) New analyses (including existing approaches applied to new data) New methodologies (e.g. for data collection, participant engagement, education) New concepts I don't know	
What is the start date of the project? (If you don't know the exact start date just select the first day of the start month. It can be in the future. If the project starts with a grant, this is the start date of the funding.)	M/d/yyyy	
What is the end date of the project? (If you don't know the exact end date just select the last day of the end month).	M/d/yyyy	
What is the expected duration of the project?	Less than 1 year 1-2 years 3-4 years 5 years or more I don't know	
Are participants currently able to contribute to citizen science activities?	Yes No I don't know	
How well can you estimate the number of observations collected by the project so far (observations as defined by the project)?	I know the approximate number I know the order of magnitude I have no idea about how many observations have been collected I don't really know what observations are Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important	
How many observations have been collected so far?	number	
How many observations have been collected so far?	0-300 301-3000 3001-30,000 30,001-300,000 More than 300,000	
How many observations are collected in a typical recent year of active project? (If the project has been running for less than a year you can estimate the number).	0-300 301-3000 More than 3000 Too difficult to estimate	To put the project's data collection in perspective just think that eBird collected 700 000 000 observations and iNaturalist 40 000 000. But that doesn't mean that you have less than 1% of the impact of these projects. Context is important and that's why we need to ask so many questions.

Annex 8 General input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
How well can you estimate the number of participants who have contributed to the project's citizen science activities?	I know the approximate number I know the order of magnitude I don't know Participants are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important	
How many participants have contributed to the project's citizen science activities so far?	number	
How many participants have contributed to the project's citizen science activities so far?	0-300 301-3000 3001-30,000 More than 30,000	
How many participants contribute to citizen science activities in a typical year of active project? (If the project has been running for less than a year you can estimate the number).	0-300 301-3000 3001-30,000 More than 30,000 Too difficult to estimate	Many citizen science projects have a "long tail" of participation, where a small minority of citizen scientists make the majority of contributions to the project (Wald, Longo, and Dobell, 2016). If the same is true in this project 10% of the participants would collect x% of observations whilst y% of observations would be collected by the remaining 90% of participants.
Including participants who have directly contributed to the citizen science activities, how many people have been engaged by the project?	0-300 301-3000 3001-30,000 30,001-300,000 More than 300,000 I don't know	
How well can you estimate the total external funding received by the project?	I know the approximate number I know the order of magnitude The project did not receive external funding I don't know	
What is the total external funding received by the project? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]	number	
What is the total external funding received by the project? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]	0-300 301-3000 3001-30,000 30,001-300,000 300,001-3,000,000 More than 300,000,000	
How well can you estimate the total financial investment in the project (including internal funding)?	I know the approximate number I know the order of magnitude The project did not receive internal funding I don't know	

Annex 8 General input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
What is the total financial investment in the project including internal funding? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]	number	
What is the total financial investment in the project including internal funding? (in £, € or \$) [Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/]	0-300 301-3000 3001-30,000 30,001-300,000 300,001-3,000,000 More than 300,000,000	
Is the project focused on one or more of the following five domains?	Economy: the production and exchange of goods and services among economic agents Environment: the bio-chemical-physical environment Governance: the processes and institutions through which decisions are made, both informal and formal Science and technology: the scientific process (method) as well as research more broadly; the scientific system, scientific paradigms and resulting technological artefacts and standards Society: individuals as well as collective (societal) values, understanding, actions and well-being (including relationships)	

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
How is the project managed?	<p>The project is run by a single organisation</p> <p>The project is run by a group of organisations but led by a single organisation</p> <p>The project is run by a group of organisations who lead equally</p> <p>The project is run by citizens</p> <p>An Artificial Intelligence is running the project</p> <p>Some other management structure</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
What type of organisation leads the project?	<p>Public bodies (including governments and municipalities)</p> <p>Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations</p> <p>Research-performing organisations (including universities)</p> <p>Some other kind of organisation</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
What types of organisations are partners in running the project?	<p>Public bodies (including governments and municipalities)</p> <p>Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations</p> <p>Research-performing organisations (including universities)</p> <p>Some other kind of organisation</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
What types of organisations are involved with the project (but don't help to manage the project)?	<p>Public bodies (including governments and municipalities)</p> <p>Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations</p> <p>Research-performing organisations (including universities)</p> <p>Some other kind of organisation</p> <p>No other organisations are involved with the project</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
Does the project have explicit health and safety regulations in place?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Not applicable</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
Is participation in the project voluntary or non-voluntary?	<p>Voluntary</p> <p>Non-voluntary (for example, pupils who have to participate as part of school activities)</p> <p>Both</p> <p>I don't know</p>	

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Are participants the object or focus of the research?	<p>They are the focus of the citizen-science research (This might be the case, for example, in health and medical research).</p> <p>They are the focus of the broader project reserach (This might be the case, for example, if the project lead is investigating motivation in citizen science projects)</p> <p>They are not the object or focus of the research.</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
Does the project research relate to human physical health (directly or indirectly)?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
How does the project aid in the investigation of diseases?	<p>Directly as part of the project activities</p> <p>Indirectly from the project activities</p> <p>It does not</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
How does the project aid in the research and development of vaccines and medical interventions?	<p>Directly as part of the project activities</p> <p>Indirectly from the project activities</p> <p>It does not</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
Does the project explicitly investigate the link between pollution and health?	<p>Yes, air pollution</p> <p>Yes, water pollution</p> <p>Yes, some other kind of pollution</p> <p>No</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
Does the project have a positive impact on the physical health of participants?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
What type of citizen science is the project according to the following categories?	<p>Contractual projects, where communities ask professional researchers to conduct a specific scientific investigation and report on the results</p> <p>Contributory projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public primarily contribute data</p> <p>Collaborative projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public contribute data but also help to refine project design, analyse data, or disseminate findings</p> <p>Co-created projects, which are designed by scientists and members of the public working together and for which at least some of the public participants are actively involved in most aspects of the research process</p> <p>Collegial projects, where non-credentialed individuals conduct research independently with varying degrees of expected recognition by institutionalised science or professionals</p> <p>The project doesn't fit any of these categories. (Jennifer won't be happy.)</p> <p>I don't know</p>	

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
In which phases of the project do participants play a role?	Identifying a research question Definition of project activities Design and development of technology and equipment for the project Collecting data Analysing data Monitoring in ways other than collecting data Passive participation (for example, contributing computer resources or social media information which is harvested by the project). Training other participants Sharing of outputs (including publication) Assessment of project impacts Acting on the results of the project Closure or handover of the project I don't know	
Do participants self-organize to carry out additional activities beyond the original scope of the project?	Yes No I don't know	
Are participants aware they are contributing to a research project?	Yes No I don't know	
Do the goals of the project align to the demands of the participants?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Are participants satisfied with the results of the project?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Are participants equal partners in the knowledge generation with the project organizers? (Knowledge generation can be understood as the conclusions drawn from the research).	Yes No; participants dominate the knowledge generation. (This is very unlikely. Please, double check before selecting this answer) No; the project organisers dominate the knowledge generation I don't know	
What is the balance between engagement and research in the project? (We know that many of you would be tempted to say they are equal in the project but we want to force you to choose one!)	Mostly engagement More engagement, but balanced More research, but balanced Mostly research I don't know	

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
What engagement strategies does the project have?	Gamification Real-time validation on observation/data submission Notification of updates to contributed observations Tips of the day Personalised recommendations Feedback on data quality Active and responsive social-media presence ("responsive" in the sense that questions from participants are responded to) Storytelling or exchanging of experiences Invitation to or suggestion of events Workshops Measurement campaigns Active and responsive pilot/case study presence ("responsive in the sense that questions from participants are responded to) A forum, or other platform on a website Awareness raising (ad-hoc demonstrations, meetings and appearances from partners) Photo contests Social events not included in previous options Creation of champions, ambassadors or leaders Organic conversation	
Does the project have a formal engagement strategy?	Yes No I don't know	
Is the engagement strategy shared with participants?	Yes No I don't know	
Do participants have multiple project activities which they can take part in?	Yes No; participants only have one activity they can take part in I don't know	
Are participants offered different levels of involvement in each project activity depending on their interest, availability and knowledge?	Yes No I don't know	
How much involvement and responsibility are offered to the participants? (with options depending on interests, availability and knowledge).	A lot of involvement and responsibility A lot of involvement, but not much responsibility Not much involvement, but a lot of responsibility Not much involvement or responsibility I don't know	

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project offer any incentives for participation?	Financial Merchandise Vouchers General equipment, such as bird-boxes Scientific equipment, such as sensors Access to media and special events Volunteering hours (for students or inmates) Co-authorship Food Education, knowledge or skills (we ask more about these in another domain) Increased sense of community Socialisation (the activity of mixing socially with others) A good excuse to avoid lockdown restrictions The project does not offer incentives for participation I don't know	
Are participants involved in similar activities outside of the project as a consequence of being involved in the project?	Yes No I don't know	
How does the project communicate with participants?	In person In print Online social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, TikTok) Blogs A forum Newsletter or email update Project website Video platforms (for example, YouTube) I don't know	Some projects experiment with rich, multimedia formats such as video. Interestingly, many people prefer news in text form. Simply put, video takes too long. You can read more here: https://digiday.com/media/despise-publisher-enthusiasm-video-people-prefer-getting-news-text/ [Image: Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2016, https://www.digitalnewsreport.org/]
Does the project include any of the following communication activities?	Hands-on experiences (for example, an interactive exhibit) Multi-directional communication (for example, a forum where all stakeholders can have a voice) Innovative means of communication (for example, TikTok) Collaboration with science-communication professionals I don't know	
Does the project have specific communication plans for specific target groups?	Yes No The project has only one target group I don't know	
Does the project create a positive change in how stakeholders communicate with one another?	Yes No I don't know	For example, new communication channels, increased frequency of communication, or more diverse methods of communication

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
As a result of this project, are channels available for participants and other stakeholders to communicate without the project?	Yes No I don't know	
How are the project outcomes shared?	Scholarly outputs e.g. peer-review publications, open data sets Grey literature e.g. reports, working papers Popular media e.g. magazine or newspaper articles, TV or radio, newsletters, leaflets, social media Events e.g. conferences, community talks lectures, workshops, fairs, seminars or webinars	
Are there plans for sustaining the collaboration between citizen scientists and other stakeholders (for example, scientists or public authorities) after the end of the project-coordination support?	Yes No There is no collaboration between citizens and other stakeholders (for example, scientists or public authorities) in the project. There are no plans to end the project-coordination support	
Is specific equipment or infrastructure required for participants to be able to contribute to project activities?	Yes No I don't know	
Are specific knowledge and skills required for individuals to participate in the project activities? For example, do participants need to be trained before they can take part?	Yes No I don't know	
What kind of specific training does the project provide to participants?	Written instructions Training video In-person training Online training The project does not provide training I don't know	
How does the project contribute to the formal education of participants (for example, by working with schools)?	Primary-level education to pupils Secondary-level education to pupils (middle and high school) Tertiary education to students (university, college and vocational courses) Adult education or life-long learning The project does not contribute to the formal education of participants. I don't know	
What support is provided to educational institutions by the project?	In-person sessions run by the project Lesson plans Educational resources (for example, work sheets or classroom activities) Explicit links to the institution's curriculum I don't know	
Do participants gain new knowledge from taking part in the project?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Do participants gain new skills from taking part in the project?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	For example: IT training (such as using a website) Equipment training (such as, using an app) Measurement training Train the trainer Training about citizen-science methodologies
Do participants gain new competencies from taking part in the project?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	Competencies are on-the-job behaviours which often require specific skills and knowledge. For example, competencies for working together, creativity and flexibility, the ability to learn, and internet savviness.
Does the project incorporate traditional or local knowledge?	Yes No I don't know	
Are support and training adapted to all relevant participant groups (e.g. participants' age, language)?	Yes No I don't know	"All relevant participant groups" refers to those people who could reasonably be expected to have an interest in participating in the project; we don't expect projects to translate all their resources into Venezuelan if the project only runs in Sweden.
Has consideration been given to allow citizen participants time and space to participate in the research given other demands and responsibilities?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project explicitly promote diversity and inclusion among all relevant participant groups?	Yes No I don't know	For example, people from ethnic minorities, or people who identify as non-binary
Does the project involve a socio-economically diverse pool of participants?	Yes No; participants are from the same socio-economical group. I don't know	Socioeconomic status is the social standing or class of an individual or group. It is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation
Where possible, has the project been designed to give access to all participants, including those with "functional diversity" [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_diversity_(disability)]?	Yes No I don't know	It is unlikely that a project can be made accessible to all potential participants. For example, it may not be possible to adapt projects which rely on participants recording observations to be accessible to individuals with visual impairments.

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Which age groups are the participants in the project?	0-10 11-20 21-40 41-60 61+	
Does the project explicitly contribute to gender equality?	Yes No I don't know	
What proportion of participants are cisgender men?	0-20% 21-40% 41-60% 61-80% 81-100%	Cisgender (sometimes cissexual, or shortened to cis) describes a person whose gender identity matches their sex assigned at birth
Does the project actively engage participants from disadvantaged or historically marginalised backgrounds?	Yes No I don't know	
Are there relevant stakeholders which the project was not able to engage?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project directly research mental health concerns?	Yes No I don't know	This paper provides an example of the context that can help to understand the question: "Developing a Citizen Social Science approach to understand urban stress and promote wellbeing in urban communities" [https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-020-0460-1]
Does the project actively raise motivation amongst participants?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	Motivation is based on the individual's desire to achieve
Does the project increase the self-efficacy of participants?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	Self-efficacy is based on an individual's belief in their own capacity to achieve
Does the project have a positive impact on the mental health of participants?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Does the project contribute to social innovation?	Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	Social innovation is the process of developing and deploying effective solutions to challenging and often systemic social and environmental issues in support of social progress. These solutions often require the active collaboration of constituents across government, business, and the non-profit world

Annex 9 Society input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
<p>Does the project foster resilience, or does it foster learning and adaptation (which then leads to resilience)?</p> <p>This is often done by fostering one of the following: (1) the will and intention to maintain social-ecological resilience (2) knowledge about the problem and the desired direction of change (3) proactive behaviour (4) the capacity to change existing patterns of behaviour.</p>	<p>Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No After five minutes, I still don't understand the question I don't know</p>	
<p>Does the project foster social capital?</p>	<p>Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know</p>	<p>Social capital is the networks of relationships among people that enable society to function effectively.</p>
<p>Do changes in participants' values, perspectives, opinions and attitudes occur as a consequence of actions carried out in the project?</p>	<p>Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know</p>	
<p>Does the project contribute to personal change in behaviour?</p>	<p>Yes and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know</p>	<p>For example, "switching from plastic bags to reusable shopping bags" or "changing an omnivorous diet to a vegan one and losing all friends in the process"</p>
<p>Does the project include objectives to protect or enhance cultural heritage components?</p>	<p>Yes No I don't know</p>	
<p>Which socially-relevant issues are directly addressed by the project?</p>	<p>Poverty Hunger and nutrition Health and wellbeing Education Gender equality Decent work and economic growth Reduced inequalities Responsible consumption and production Peace, justice and strong institutions</p>	

Annex 10 Governance input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Is the project team aware of what the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are?	Yes No I don't know	
Is the project at all related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?	Yes No I don't know	
Which of the following Sustainable Development Goals is the project related to?	(1) No Poverty (2) Zero Hunger (3) Good Health and Well-being (4) Quality Education (5) Gender Equality (6) Clean Water and Sanitation (7) Affordable and Clean Energy (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth (9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (10) Reducing Inequality (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities (12) Responsible Consumption and Production (13) Climate Action (14) Life Below Water (15) Life On Land (16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions (17) Partnerships for the Goals	
Does the project include data which match a specific indicator of a Sustainable Development Goal?	Yes No I don't know	
Which of the following indicators does the project collect data related to?	[List of SDG indicators]	
Does the project contribute data to the official reporting for a Sustainable Development Goal indicator?	Yes No I don't know	
Are the outputs generated by the project open access?	Yes; all outputs Yes: some outputs No I don't know	
Are data access rights clear and transparent?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project have a code of ethics?	Yes No I don't know	Here's an example that you can use
Is the code of ethics made available to participants?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project involve the collection of personal data of the participants? (Personal data is any information that relates to an identified, or identifiable, living individual.)	Yes, at least sometimes No I don't know	

Annex 10 Governance input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project explicitly state which ethical procedures it follows to ensure the data are collected and processed lawfully? (See, for example [mics.tools/.../Ethics requirements: Protection of personal data].)	Yes No The project is not about data collection, and doesn't collect or process personal data The project doesn't need to ensure the data are collected lawfully I don't know	
Does the project include opportunities for project leaders and participants to discuss the ethical and political dimensions of the research carried out?	Yes No The research element of the project is not significant I don't know	
Are citizens informed about how the data collected and analysed by the project are used?	Yes No I don't know	
Are citizens informed about where the data collected by the project are stored?	Yes No I don't know	
Are citizens informed about whether the data collected by the project are shared?	Yes No I don't know	
Do participants have to explicitly give consent (for example, signing a consent form) to take part in the project? (See, for example [mics.tools/.../Ethics requirements: Participant informed-consent procedures].)	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project explicitly foster co-ownership of the project among participants and other stakeholders?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project make sure that those with less power, women, and minorities are among those who are asking the questions?	Yes No or not yet I don't know	<p>Whether the scientific questions to be addressed by a citizen science project come from citizens themselves or civic educators - including scientists, professional researchers, and their institutions - needs to be interrogated.</p> <p>Is it reasonable to expect communities to ask the questions? Is it overambitious to assume that they can? Does suggesting that they cannot indicate a level of institutional and structural racism?</p> <p>Empowering people includes enabling them to drive citizen-science projects. (Ceccaroni et al., 2021)</p>

Annex 10 Governance input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project explicitly foster new collaborations amongst different stakeholders (not including those between citizens and scientists; so, for example, between public bodies and commercial organisations)?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project lead to an increased level of trust among stakeholders and other participants?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Does the project work with other organisations to involve specific target groups or individuals (for example, a river trust for water-quality monitoring or a local community action group)?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project collaborate with other initiatives to enhance mutual learning?	Yes No I don't know	
Which resources does the project share with other initiatives?	Data Learnings Partiicipants Instruments (for example, measuring ktis) Methodologies Resources on the theory and practice of citizen science Communication channels Other resources I don't know	
<p>This question refers to the "institutional changes" a project contributes to, which EU funded projects are required to consider.</p> <p>Institutions are "systems of rules, beliefs, norms and organizations that together generate a regularity of (social) behaviour".</p> <p>The institutional change is usually measured along the following six dimensions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open access/data 2. Ethics 3. Gender equality 4. Public engagement 5. Science education 6. Responsible research and innovation <p>Based on these 'dimensions', what institutional change does the project contribute to (within the organisations associated with the project)?</p>	<p>Open access/data: for example, development of an organisational Data Management Plan</p> <p>Ethics: for example, creation of an ethics board or employment of a quality assurance officer</p> <p>Gender equality: for example, development of a Gender Equality Plan</p> <p>Public engagement: for example, specialists interacting with non-specialists</p> <p>Science education: for example, teaching and learning of science to non-scientists</p> <p>Responsible research and innovation: for example, development of practices that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness or sustainability of research and innovation processes and products</p> <p>I don't know</p>	
Have the organisations involved in the project increased their commitment to or investment in citizen science as a result of being involved in the project?	Yes, they have made a formal committment Yes, but not as a formal commitment No I don't know	
Does the project lead to an increase in the commitment of organizations to public participation in decision making?	Yes, they have made a formal committment Yes, but not as a formal commitment No I don't know	

Annex 10 Governance input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project help organisations to increase their capacity for public participation in decision making?	Yes No I don't know	For example, the project could provide training or resources.
Are the participants satisfied with the process of participation in the project?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Are participants more actively involved in political process as a result of taking part in the project?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Does the project's data or findings lead to the enforcement of existing regulations or policies?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project have any explicit impact on external organisational policy (for example, the Outfall Safari project causing a change in the policies of Thames Water)?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project explicitly inform any governmental policy process?	Yes, at the local level Yes, at the regional level Yes, at the national level Yes, at the international level No I don't know	

Annex 11 Economy input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
How has the project been funded?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal funding of the coordinating organisation(s) • Micro funding • Crowdfunding • Private foundations or non-governmental organisations • Corporate sponsors / funders • Government funding or appropriation • Other national sponsors / funders • European Union (for example, via Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe) • Other international sponsors / funders • I don't know 	<p>There is a general connection between all forms of alternative funding: they all provide access to capital for a segment of the population that cannot access it through traditional means. However, there are significant differences between micro funding and crowdfunding. Micro funding includes microfinance and social (peer-to-peer) lending, and is not commonly used in citizen science. Microfinance provides loans and other basic financial services to the poor. Social lending gives ordinary people the ability to lend around the world.</p>
Did the project generate related new projects?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • It's in progress (for example, a project proposal has been written) • No • I don't know 	
In total, how much external funding has been received for these new projects?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 – 3000 • 3001 - 30 000 • 30 001 - 300 000 • 300 001 - 3 000 000 • More than 3 000 000 	
Does the project generate new jobs among the organisations running the project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project generate new jobs in external organisations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project involve commercial activities related to industry or academia?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes (for example, commercialisation of tools or technology developed within the project) • No • I don't know 	<p>While a level of scepticism exists towards business involvement in citizen science, some observe that the sector has made positive and impactful contributions towards advancing the tools and application of citizen science as well as in providing participants through campaigns that engage employees.</p>

Annex 11 Economy input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project include any competitive advantage (on the economic, rather than the scientific scale)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p>Here “competitive advantage” refers to factors that allow an organisation to produce outputs or services better or more cheaply than its rivals.</p> <p>For example, incorporation of citizen science might provide a competitive advantage for the ecotourism providers in the tourism market; healthcare data might provide a competitive advantage for pharmaceutical companies.</p>
Does the project explicitly promote the formation and growth of micro-, small- or medium-sized enterprises / businesses?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project increase demand for the services of external organisations (for example, by promoting sustainable tourism)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes; the project doubled the GDP of a country • Yes; but it wasn't that successful • No • I don't know 	
<p>Does the project have an explicit exploitation plan?</p> <p>Exploitation is defined as the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking. Exploitation plans often include generating new business models.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project have any concrete cooperation in place for the exploitation of results?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project have explicit plans to sustain the project activities after the current funding received has ended?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project require recurring investments in technology (for example, software licences or app/platform maintenance) that affect its long-term sustainability?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project have explicit links with public authorities?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p>For example, having them as partners of the consortium managing the project, as part of the advisory board, or as regular attendants of communication activities</p>

Annex 11 Economy input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project have any economic potential to be exploited in the future (for example, new intellectual property with economic value, or new sensors with a clear market)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project explicitly contribute to the reduction of government expenditure? "Not yet, but it might one day?" Don't worry, you can always come back and update your answers on the MICS platform when it does.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Does the project explicitly contribute to the reduction of costs for other external organisations? By, for example, increasing the availability of data to external organisations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	
Is the citizen science used in the project more cost-efficient than using experts and traditional scientific methods?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has not been estimated • It has been estimated and there is no clear winner from the purely economic point of view. • Citizen science clearly produces savings in comparison with using experts or traditional scientific methods. • We know that it can be awkward to admit that citizen science is more expensive or less efficient than traditional methods, but here is the option to do so • I don't know 	
By using citizen scientists (rather than professionals) is the project able to cover a larger sample size (i.e., to collect or analyse a larger amount of data)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Not relevant for the project • Too difficult to say • I don't know 	
What are the estimated, typical, annual personnel costs (in £, € or \$)?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 3000 • 3000-30,000 • 30,000-300,000 • More than 300,000 • I don't know 	

Annex 11 Economy input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
<p>Excluding personnel costs, what is the estimated, approximate cost per observation (in £, € or \$) (observations as defined by the project)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying their cost is not important. • Less than 2 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.) • 2-8 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of three sevenths of the world population.) • 9-32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of two sevenths of the world population.) • More than 32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.) • I don't know 	
<p>What are the estimated, typical, annual costs of IT systems for data collection and management (in £, € or \$) (for example for the use of Amazon Web Services or other cloud-computing services)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 300 • 300-3000 • 3000-30,000 • More than 30,000 • I don't know 	
<p>How much time is invested by the project in training citizens?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project does not train participants • Not much (hours) • Some (days) • A lot (there are one or more people, or a work package, explicitly dedicated to training citizens) • Too difficult to quantify • I don't know 	<p>Training might involve identifying different species or planets, using equipment or sensors, or analysing data, and can include the production of training materials.</p>
<p>How many hours, on average, does a participant dedicate to the project in a typical recent year? We acknowledge that this can vary hugely from participant to participant; go with an average participant.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 3 • 3-30 • More than 30 • The project has no participants • I don't know 	
<p>Do participants have to pay to take part in the project?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, at least in some cases • No • I don't know 	

Annex 11 Economy input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
What is this payment used for?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• General support to an organisation• Equipment/services given to the participants• Training given to the participants• I don't know	
Can participants make a voluntary financial contribution to the project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Yes (for example, Patreon supporter)• No• I don't know	

Annex 12 Environment input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Which environmental policy frameworks does the project consider?	Organisational frameworks, such as Goldman Sachs Environmental Policy Framework Local frameworks, such as Central Bedfordshire Environmental Framework Regional frameworks, such as Massachusetts Sustainable Water Management Initiative (SWMI) Framework National frameworks, such as the U.K. Environment Agency framework Global frameworks, such as UNEP Environmental, social and sustainability framework The project does not consider any environmental policy frameworks I don't know	
Which environmental issues are related to the aims of the project? (We'll ask details about each issue later.)	Sustainable agriculture Freshwater Affordable and clean energy Sustainable cities and communities Air quality Responsible consumption and production (including food waste and chemical pollution) Climate action Marine water Life on land	
Do the project activities include pro-environmental actions e.g. litter picking?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project help to identify the location of environmental issues?	Yes No I don't know	For example, the project identifies which sections of a river are polluted or which areas of a city have high levels of air pollution.
Does the project inform how a natural resource or ecosystem is managed?	Yes No I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project monitor ecosystem services?	Yes No I don't know	The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment – a four-year United Nations assessment of the condition and trends of the world's ecosystems - categorizes ecosystem services as: Provisioning Services or the provision of food, fresh water, fuel, fiber, and other goods; Regulating Services such as climate, water, and disease regulation as well as pollination; Supporting Services such as soil formation and nutrient cycling; and Cultural Services such as educational, aesthetic, and cultural heritage values as well as recreation and tourism.
How does the project contribute to sustainable agriculture?	Increasing the proportion of agricultural area being managed sustainably Increasing investment in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and technology development Researching sustainable agriculture	
Does the project contribute to secure plant and animal genetic resources in either medium- or long-term conservation facilities?	Yes No I don't know	
With regards to clean water and sanitation, which of the following activities does the project include?	Monitors / has a measurable impact on / both Ambient water quality/pollution Water-related ecosystems Involving local communities in water management Water-use efficiency Water stress of water scarcity Correct treatment of wastewater	
How does the project contribute to affordable and clean energy? (Clean energy includes sources like sunlight, wind, rain, tides, waves, and geothermal heat.)	Increasing the share of clean energy in the energy mix Increasing energy efficiency Researching clean energy	
With regards to clean air and sustainable cities, which of the following activities does the project include?	Monitors / has a measurable impact on / both Involving local communities in urban planning and management Correct collection and treatment of solid waste Ambient air quality/pollution (including fine particulate matter e.g. PM2.5 and PM10) Green public spaces	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
With regards to responsible consumption and production, which of the following activities does the project include?	Monitors / has a measurable impact on / both Food waste Harmful chemical in the air Harmful chemical in the water Harmful chemical in the soil Waste generation and management (including prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse)	
Does the project explicitly disseminate information on sustainable development or lifestyles?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project educate participants on environmental challenges?	Yes No I don't know	
With regards to life below water (marine water, not freshwater), which of the following activities does the project include?	Monitors / has a measurable impact on / both Marine nutrient pollution Marine plastic pollution Ocean acidification Marine protected areas Marine technology	
With regards to life on land, which of the following activities does the project include?	Monitors / has a measurable impact on / both Sustainable management of forests Desertification or land degradation Mountain ecosystems Other terrestrial ecosystems Biodiversity Species extinction Invasive alien species Wildlife poaching or trafficking	
Does the project include objectives to protect or enhance natural resources?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project collaborate with external companies to enable the adoption of sustainable practices?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project explicitly contribute to a higher awareness of, or positive attitude towards, the natural environment, on this planet or others?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, I think so No I don't know	
Does the project lead to an increased stewardship of the natural environment among participants?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, I think so No I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Which disciplines are involved in the project?	Citizen science (If you don't select this one, you are in trouble) Agricultural and veterinary sciences (including, forestry sciences, fisheries sciences, and land and farm management) Art theory and criticism Biological sciences (including ecology, zoology, genetics, and biodiversity) Chemical sciences (including medicinal and biomolecular chemistry) Earth sciences (including geology, atmospheric sciences, and oceanography) Engineering (including food sciences, environmental engineering, and biomedical engineering) Environmental sciences (including ecological applications, environmental management, and soil sciences) Information and computing sciences (including artificial intelligence and image processing, distributed computing, and computer software) Language, communication and culture (including linguistics, and literary studies) Law and legal studies Mathematical sciences and statistics Medical and health sciences (including neurosciences, public health and health services, nutrition and dietetics, and human movement and sports science) Philosophy and religious studies (including applied ethics, and history and philosophy of specific fields) Physical sciences (including astronomical and space sciences, atomic, molecular, nuclear, particle and plasma physics, and quantum physics) Psychology and cognitive sciences Studies in human society (including human geography, policy and administration, sociology, and education) Technology (including communications technologies, and computer hardware) I don't know	
Does the project explicitly promote interdisciplinary ways of working?	Yes No I don't know	
What is the scope of the research? (The project, for example, studies plastic pollution worldwide.)	National Multinational Global Galactic I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Is the project's citizen science basic or applied?	Basic Applied Both Too difficult to distinguish I don't know	Basic science, such as understanding how cells work, is research aimed at understanding fundamental problems. Applied science, such as the medical field, is the application of basic scientific knowledge to solve practical problems
Is the project's research inductive or deductive?	Inductive Deductive Both Too difficult to distinguish I don't know	Inductive reasoning is described as a method where one's experiences and observations are synthesised to come up with a general truth. Many dictionaries define inductive reasoning as deriving general principles from specific observations: "bottom-up logic". Deductive reasoning, or "top-down logic", is the process of reasoning from one or more hypotheses to reach a logical conclusion.
Do participants take part in systematic or convenience data-collection?	Systematic data-collection (for example, data collected from a vessel along a transect) Convenience data-collection (for example, data collected from a vessel of opportunity like a ferry) Both Data collection is not a significant element of the project. I don't know	Convenience data-collection or sampling - also known as grab sampling, accidental sampling, or opportunistic sampling - is a type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. This type of sampling is the most common in citizen science.
Does the project have have a data management plan?	Yes No I don't know	A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated
Does the project have a risk management plan?	Yes No I don't know	Risk in the context of project management rather than risk to the participants.
The following four questions focus on the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'. They focus on the data generated by the project, rather than on other outputs. Are the data generated by the project findable?	Yes No I don't know	To be findable, data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier and are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Are the data generated by the project accessible?	Yes No I don't know	To be accessible, data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol. The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
Are the data generated by the project interoperable?	Yes No I don't know	To be interoperable, data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
Are the data generated by the project reusable?	Yes No I don't know	To be reusable, data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license and meet domain-relevant community standards.
Are project data available through APIs?	Yes No I don't know	An application programming interface (API) is a connection between computers or between computer programs. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.
Do other stakeholders have more access to project data than participants (for example, access to raw data)?	Yes No I don't know	
What processes are defined in the project to guarantee high data-quality?	Data profiling - Initially assessing the data to understand their current state, often including value distributions Data standardization - Ensuring that data conform to standards Data monitoring - Keeping track of data quality over time and reporting variations in the quality of data Peer-to-peer validation - More-expert participants validating observations by less-expert participants Expert validation – professionals validating observations by participants Automated strategies: Matching or linking - A way to compare data so that similar but slightly different records can be aligned; matching may use "fuzzy logic" to find duplicates in the data; it can for example recognise that "Sasha Wood" and "Sasha Woods" may be the same individual. Automated strategies: Artificial intelligence - For example, improving image or audio classification by using computer vision or computer hearing I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
On a scale of 1 to 3 (1 being "partially" and 3 being "completely") how would you score how the data collected in the project answer the question posed at the start of the project?	1 2 3 The project does not collect data Not relevant to the project I don't know	
Does the project link participants to experts (for example, to validate data)?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project provide data visualisations such as graphs, maps and animations?	Yes No I don't know	
Are the project data used in models or forecasting?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project have or adopt a code of research or a research integrity policy available to participants? (See, for example [https://ukrio.org/publications/code-of-practice-for-research/])	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project investigate the social or psychological needs or behaviours of non-human animals?	Yes No I don't know	
Does participation in the project increase participants' scientific literacy?	Yes No I don't know	Scientific literacy is the knowledge and understanding of scientific concepts and processes required for personal decision making, participation in civic and cultural affairs, and economic productivity.
Does the project formally build on existing citizen-science expertise in the specific field of research?	Yes No I don't know	
Is new knowledge developed regarding how best to incorporate citizens into research design?	Yes, and formally documented Yes, but not formally documented No I don't know	
How many publications, indexed by Google Scholar, resulted from the project?	The project has not produced any publications Less than 3 3-30 More than 30 I don't know	
How many open-access publications, indexed by Google Scholar, resulted from the project?	The project has not produced any open-access publications Less than 3 3-30 More than 30 I don't know	
How many citations have the publications produced by the project received, in total (according to Google scholar)?	Less than 3 3-30 31-300 More than 300 I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
What is the highest impact-factor (or impact-index) of the publications produced by the project? (Just Google: "[journal name]" impact factor)	Less than 2 2-5 More than 5 I don't know	
How is the involvement of participants formally recognised in publications?	Individual authorship Group pseudonym as (co-)author Individuals acknowledged by name Group of participants collectively acknowledged Participants are not formally recognised in publications I don't know	When the project does produce publications, you may wish to use a group pseudonym, such as "on behalf of the consortium", as Rambaut et al did https://virological.org/t/preliminary-genomic-characterisation-of-an-emergent-sars-cov-2-lineage-in-the-uk-defined-by-a-novel-set-of-spike-mutations/563
Has the project supported student's dissertations or theses?	Yes It's in progress No I don't know	
How many stakeholders have shown an active interest in the results of the project? (for example, downloaded results from the project website)	Less than 3 3-30 31-300 301-3000 More than 3000 I don't know	
What technology does the project use or develop?	Uses a pre-existing version / Develops a new version / Both Apps Sensors Artificial intelligence Platforms (a range of services available on the Internet including marketplaces, search engines and social media) Digital solutions (digitalising old methodologies, processes or technology: e.g. Trello is a project management solution; Slack is a communication solution) We don't use technology	
Does the project explicitly promote the development, transfer or dissemination of environmentally-sound technologies (documented, for example, in a dissemination plan)?	Yes No I don't know	Environmentally sound technologies are techniques and technologies capable of reducing environmental damage through processes and materials that generate fewer potentially damaging substances, recover such substances from emissions prior to discharge, or utilize and recycle production residues.
Does the project use mobile phones as a primary tool (for example, using an app to collect observations)?	Yes No I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Is participation possible without a phone connected to the internet?	No; it's nearly impossible Yes; participation is possible without a phone, but a computer connected to the internet is necessary. Yes; participation is possible without a phone or a computer connected to the internet. I don't know	
Does the project provide technical support to participants?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project use enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project enhance international cooperation on science, technology or innovation?	Yes No I don't know	
Are participants exposed to steps in the scientific process in a systematic manner?	Yes No, it has not been considered No, it would not be appropriate for this project I don't know	For example, are they presented with the problem before they are presented with the method? Are they exposed to the results before they are given the conclusion.
Are participants able to challenge the project's methodologies?	Yes, and this could result in methodologies changing Yes, but this could not result in methodologies changing (because, for example, data need to be compared with existing datasets or because some SDG indicator is determining the parameters to measure, even if they don't necessarily make sense in a particular location) No I don't know	
Does the project provide participants with easy and explicit access to pertinent research findings or important literature used to inform the project before research begins?	Yes No I don't know	

Annex 13 Science input feature table

Question	Answer options	Help
Does the project have a formal dissemination strategy?	Yes No I don't know	<p>Unsure how dissemination differs from communication?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. - Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising that makes research results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work.
Are participants explicitly encouraged to reflect on or discuss current values, perspectives, opinions and attitudes relating to science concepts?	Yes No I don't know	
Does the project positively influence the attitudes of participants regarding science?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Does the project increase the interest of participants in the topic of the research?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Are participants explicitly exposed to various careers in science through the project?	Yes No I don't know	
Are participants more likely to consider a scientific career having participated in the project?	Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know	
Are project leaders challenged to consider novel connections between their own careers and research, and the context of participating citizens?	Yes No I don't know	